

D1.13 Scientific Roadmap and Innovation Management Evaluation

WP1 - Project Management

Version: 1.00

SPHINX

A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for
Health-Care Industry

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Executive Summary

This report presents the final updates and results for the Scientific and Innovation roadmap of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) research and innovation project SPHINX. The document describes the set of actions that were carried out within SPHINX necessary to achieve the SPHINX vision, and guidelines to assist cyber security industry and scientists to address externalities in order to improve innovation and competitiveness which will in turn have a significant impact on the main beneficiaries of SPHINX, the healthcare sector. It also describes the different pathways that were taken by the SPHINX Consortium to ensure that project innovations are captured, secured and promoted.

In addition, this document defines our Innovation Management Plan, inspired by the “Innovation Radar” (De Prato, 2015), a DG Connect / JRC-IPTS support initiative that is part of the EURIPIDIS project - European Innovation Policies for the Digital Shift, which includes a multiple step assessment of the maturity of the innovations developed within the project and allows us to provide guidance during the project on the most appropriate steps to increase the innovation potential and the innovator capacity.

D1.13 is based on the previous updated version of the D1.2 (that included the intermediate updates, and was submitted on M23) and is extended to include updates concerning the final outcomes of the SPHINX innovation management phases, namely the ones stemming from the Building a Business Case phase; in this direction, the input from an online questionnaire, specific to each SPHINX innovation (i.e. developed component/solution), was used towards eliciting insights from the partners involved in the development of the SPHINX innovations. These insights facilitated the development of the SPHINX Business model, using the Business Model Canvas methodology.

In section 2.3, an index with the updated material contained in D1.13 is available.

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Table of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	EXPLANATION
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ENISA	Agency for Network and Information Security
e-PHI	Electronic Protected Health Information
IPS	intrusion prevention systems
SLA	A service-level agreement
IMS	innovation management system

ABBREVIATION	EXPLANATION
ISP	Innovation Strategy Plan
IP	Intellectual property
CA	Consortium Agreement
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses Opportunities, Threats
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
MoM	Minutes of Meeting
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ARC	Average of Relative Citations
R&D	Research and development
VAaaS	Vulnerability Assessment as a Service
ICT	information and communications technology
NCPs	National Contact Points

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This research and innovation roadmap is an important tool towards achieving SPHINX's strategic objectives by assisting the cybersecurity industry and academia to address externalities in order to improve innovation and competitiveness for the benefit of the healthcare sector and naturally to all patients/citizens. The roadmap, along with the community being built around it, focuses on giving good practice messages about cybersecurity issues in the healthcare sector, which has been selected by the SPHINX project as the one to be addressed (although many of the technical developments to be accomplished within the SPHINX project will be applicable to many other economic sectors). The research and innovation roadmap focus on the steps necessary for realising the best use of innovative cybersecurity solutions. More specifically, the research and innovation roadmap focuses on what research, knowledge, technologies, or skills are necessary, to capture the benefits associated with securing the use of data (namely personal and health data) in healthcare systems, reinforcing patients' confidence in smart health and assisted living, hence fostering a wider societal acceptance, leading to an enhancement of the quality of care to patients. Thus, the aim of this deliverable is to provide a research and innovation roadmap that presents the research and innovation output needed to capture positive externalities associated with cyber security in the healthcare sector and diminish negative ones to obtain the best societal impact, develop the necessary skills and contribute to technology and cyber security standardisation.

1.2 Road mapping methodology

The road mapping process built upon the current work within the SPHINX project, and hence slightly deviates from common road mapping method proposals and guidelines, which usually incorporate the creation of a vision and suggest conducting interviews with experts and holding several focus group discussions and workshops with relevant stakeholders. Such parts of the road mapping process are already embedded in the SPHINX project work and timeline and will produce several deliverables that report the project's findings and outcomes. Thus, standard road mapping processes were adapted to review such deliverables and incorporate their findings into the relevant parts of the road mapping, rather than redoing the tasks. The development process of the present research and innovation roadmap done in three phases, adapting several recommendations and guidelines for the development of roadmaps to the SPHINX project:

1. Planning and preparation.
2. Visioning.
3. Development.
4. Continuous Evaluation

Road mapping is by definition a living process that incorporates the evolution of the roadmap after its finalisation, as well as its implementation, monitoring and updating, hence, a fourth phase is envisioned to be carried by the SPHINX Community during and after completion of the road mapping (and of the SPHINX project as whole).

The remaining of the document is structured the following way, Section 3, will detail how SPHINX conducted innovation management planning, controlling and monitoring of innovations, identified enablers and drove factors that fostered innovation. Section 4, describes the Scientific Roadmap for Cybersecurity in Healthcare, focusing on both medium-term and short-term expected technological and scientific advancements. Finally, we conclude this document with a short section with conclusions.

1.3 Updated material

Final updates	
Updated section	Updates description
Executive summary	Updates in the executive summary section
3.13.3.4	Updates on the activities related to the development of the SPHINX business model
3.13.3.6	Innovation Radar tool questionnaires results
5	Updates in the Conclusions
Intermediate updates	
Updated section	Updates description
3.13	Results from the Exploration, Definition & Characterisation, building a use case phases.

2 Background: Scientific Challenges in Cyber Security for the Health-Care Industry.

The healthcare sector faces numerous challenges as it transitions from paper to digital record-keeping, through the advancements of technology and the Internet. As the healthcare industry moves to adopt new technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), wireless and networked medical devices, in addition to mobile and web-based applications, it has fallen behind in ensuring the security of electronic protected health information (e-PHI) and as a consequence, to ensure patients' rights in terms of Data Privacy. Equally worrying, clinical systems and medical devices have historically not been designed around any cyber security framework that enforces Privacy and Security by design, leading to an increased opportunity for technology savvy criminals to exploit them for fun and/or profit, with potentially catastrophic consequences to patients (David Arney, 2011). Using systems, the way they were designed, often causes gaps in security. With the increased value of medical information, organizations need to find ways to properly assess vendors and devices before installing and deploying them within their organizations. (David Arney, 2011) examines the regulations, such as The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996, and security features of networked medical devices by identifying security requirements, the principal threats and the challenges involved in addressing them, focusing not only on attack models, but also on a model for networked medical devices. A patient's privacy and safety may be jeopardized due to inadequate security that would enable malicious attacks using malware to compromise patient information or even worse cause physical harm (David Arney, 2011). The research described in (David Arney, 2011) addresses the following questions: What government regulations are needed to improve the security and safety standards for the medical device industry? Will medical devices support encryption and anti-virus? Are access controls like RBAC supported for authorization?

Traditionally, medical devices have been used in a stand-alone mode or have had limited network connectivity, typically to a proprietary subnet of similar devices (e.g., a patient monitoring network). However, economic pressures, the increasing use of IT, and the desire to improve staff efficiency and quality of care have led to a usage model where more devices are integrated with the larger hospital IT infrastructure. Attractive price points and lower maintenance costs make standard Internet protocol (IP) networks the technology of choice. Similarly, device manufacturers increasingly utilize commercial technologies, standard operating systems, or other off-the-shelf software components, as well as commercial central processing unit (CPU) platforms (Wirth, 2011). Although the economic benefit of this approach is clear, it has introduced vulnerabilities and is exposing medical devices to common cyberthreats. Additionally, a device's proprietary software denies access for the organisation, to add security measures to the device. As medical devices incorporate more information technologies for added features, the complexity of critical devices may affect the safety of the patient and or the device. In the US, Healthcare organizations receive a Manufacturer Disclosure Statement for Medical Device Security (MDS2) that provides security related information regarding the security features that are supported (Keller, 2017). However, the device may not support encryption, anti-virus, or account credentials. Another issue is that the typical life cycle of the device is longer than the life cycle of the operating system. Due to the regulatory compliance and validations that manufacturers must follow, these operating systems can no longer be patched (Wirth, 2011). Similarly, the European Union enacted the Medical Device Regulation of 2017 (Regulation (EU) 2017/745) which applies to every manufacturer, authorized representative, importer or distributor of medical devices, regulatory affairs or quality management professional.

While regulatory compliance standards are already being met by the manufacturers, there may still be gaps between the medical device security and the policies and or procedures of the healthcare facility. So how then does the healthcare sector go about assessing the risk or lack of security to protect patient's information that may or may not be stored on the physical device?

3 The Sphinx Innovation Roadmap for Cybersecurity in Healthcare

3.1 Innovation Management Methodology

The SPHINX consortium has a very strong focus on innovation, therefore it must provide itself with the right means to assess the maturity of innovations developed within the project and to gain guidance during the project on the most appropriate steps to increase the innovation potential and the innovator's capacity.

This section of deliverable D1.2, describes how SPHINX shall conduct innovation management planning, controlling and monitoring of innovations. The objective of innovation management in SPHINX, is to periodically assess innovation potential and innovator's capacity, focusing on the main innovations identified within the scope of the project, so to gain full awareness of their current status and develop improvement actions aimed to achieve all the innovation objectives of the project. SPHINX will maintain an innovation management system (IMS) during the whole project. This IMS is intended to be a set of interrelated or interacting elements of an organization to establish innovation policies and objectives, and processes to achieve those objectives, in line with different standards (as the CEN/TS 16555-1(RD02)).

The SPHINX Project approach to Innovation Management is basically inspired by the "Innovation Radar". The Innovation Radar (IR) is a DG Connect / JRC-IPTS support initiative that is part of the EURIPIDIS project, a 3-year joint project between DG Connect and JRC-IPTS, launched in August 2013.

The Innovation Radar provides up-to-date intelligence on the innovative output of EU-funded research projects and can be intended as a tool for monitoring the progress of innovations and innovators.

The main elements of the Innovation Radar involve:

- Assessing the maturity of innovations developed within the EU projects and identifying high potential innovators and innovations.
- Providing guidance during the project on the most appropriate steps to reach the market.
- Supporting innovators through entrepreneurship initiatives to cover specific needs concerning networking, access to finance, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

Two indicators have been built with the Innovation Radar data. The first is the **Innovation Potential Indicator** which aims to measure H2020 projects' innovation development towards commercialisation. The second is the **Innovator Capacity Indicator** which aims to capture the innovative capacity of the innovators behind these innovations.

In the business world innovation management is the process through which a business systematically develops a new product, service, process, or business model. Within SPHINX we aim to develop a series of services as part of a toolkit for assessing and reducing cyber risks in hospitals and care centres.

While organizations come up with new innovations all the time ranging from different ways to package and ship goods to the development of new technologies that enable customers to shop in more seamless ways, the manner in which they manage innovation can vary greatly depending on the industry and organization. In fact, innovation management itself can take many forms, and can have vastly different impact in terms of scope and value for the business. Within SPHINX we will apply innovation management as a means to provide value to our key stakeholders in the healthcare industry and significantly boost the communication and exploitation

activities of the project by feeding them with tangible results regarding the scientific and technological achievements of SPHINX.

Section 3.2 defines the steps necessary for realising the best use of innovative Cybersecurity solutions. More specifically, the innovation management roadmap focuses on what research, knowledge, technologies, and skills are necessary, to capture the benefits associated with securing the use of data (namely personal and health data) in healthcare systems, reinforcing patients' confidence in smart health and assisted living, hence fostering a wider societal acceptance, leading to an enhancement of the quality of care to patients.

3.2 SPHINX Innovation MGT Phases

Within SPHINX innovation management will be organised into three key phases:

- Exploration (link with the research activities)
- Definition (link with the technical activities)
- Building of business case (link with Communication and Exploitation activities)

In the **Exploration phase**, the aim is to identify core problems that the SPHINX project is trying to solve. In the **Definition phase**, the aim is to uncover the best ways to prototype and develop the underpinning technologies of SPHINX so that may help to solve the problems identified in the Exploration phase. In the **Building a Business Case** phase, the aim is to ensure that an investment in the innovations of SPHINX will see strong returns which will drive actual business growth for every organisation involved.

The next sections describe the phase in more detail and link the theory to the tangible results implemented within the project by means of a series of appropriate tools for each phase that will help both partners define and describe their innovations.

3.3 Innovation Potential Indicators

The Innovation Potential Indicators encompass three indicators that capture essential steps in the innovation development process.

- **Innovation readiness:** this indicator relates to the technical maturity of evolving innovations. It aims to define the development phase of innovations. It accounts for the steps undertaken to prepare them for commercialisation (e.g. prototyping, demonstration or testing activities or a feasibility study) and to secure their technological resources. Furthermore, this indicator considers the time to the potential commercialisation.
- **Innovation management:** this indicator addresses the consortium and its commitment to bring innovations to the market. It aims to measure the capability of management teams to transform new technologies or research results into marketable products or services. To this purpose, this indicator includes, among others, clarifying the related ownership and IPR issues, preparing a business plan or market study, securing capital investment from public and private sources, or engaging potential end-users in the project.
- **Market potential:** this indicator relates to the demand and supply side of innovations. Regarding the demand side, it concerns the prospective market conditions and the chances of successful commercialisation. It aims to assess how products or services satisfy a market sector and serve a potential customer base. With respect to the supply side, it aims to assess whether there are potential barriers (e.g. regulatory frameworks or existing IPR issues) which could weaken the commercial exploitation of innovations.

3.4 Innovator Capacity Indicator

The Innovator Capacity Indicator encompasses two indicators that capture the capacity of innovators in conducting and delivering successful innovations.

- **Innovator's ability:** this indicator relates to the ability of organisations in developing innovations within the EU-funded activities. It accounts for the number of times organisations have been identified by the Innovation Radar as key innovators. It includes other factors such as reviewers' opinions about innovators' potential and independence in fulfilling the market potential of innovations.
- **Innovator's environment:** this indicator aims to capture the overall conditions in the project consortium which an innovator faces. It relates to the composition and activity of partner organisations, the performance of the project in terms of innovations, and the commitment of relevant partners to exploiting innovations. Moreover, it also considers the presence of organisations that are directly interested in exploiting the innovations. It is assumed that a positive environment will have positive knowledge spill-overs between innovators and their environments.

3.5 Innovation Analysis

The two aforementioned indicators are calculated based on the results of an assessment on the project / initiative and on the potential innovations identified within them. The assessment is strictly guided by an assessment questionnaire, a score table and a method. Once the indicators are calculated for a given project, the results can be used to evaluate the "Maturity Level" of the innovations assessed.

Four innovation categories have been created based on respective scores of the Innovation Management and Innovation Readiness Indicators.

The four categories are represented in following figure.

Figure 1: Innovation Management Analysis

Optimisation: this category includes innovations outperforming in innovation management and innovation readiness. These innovations are technologically mature and show high commitment of the project consortium to bring them to the market. They are considered ‘Ready for the market’.

Creation: this category includes innovations progressing on technology development process (e.g. pilots, prototypes, demonstration). They are considered ‘Advanced on technology preparation’. In order to capitalise on the potential of these innovations, the management team needs to focus on transforming a new technology or research results into a marketable product or service and to prepare its commercialisation.

Commitment: this category includes innovations for which concrete market-oriented ideas have been put together (e.g. market studies, business plans, end-user engagement). They are considered ‘Advanced on market preparation’. Their commercialisation depends on progressing on technology development.

Exploration: This category includes innovations, which actively explore value creation opportunities. They are considered ‘Getting things started’. These innovations are in the early phases of technological readiness, but already show high commitment levels from the organisations developing them. Their commercialisation requires efforts in transforming technology into marketable products. Alternatively, this category includes concrete market-oriented ideas, which depend on further progressing on technology development process.

The Optimisation category comprises all innovations that record a score equal or higher than the average score, plus one standard deviation on the Innovation Management and Innovation Readiness Indicators respectively (see figure above). The reference point to construct the border of this segment is point A that represents innovations with an average score plus one standard deviation on both indicators. The border is then drawn along a circular segment, where the radius is defined as the radial distance of point A to the optimal situation (a score of 100 on both indicators). Employing a circular border has several advantages. First, all innovations on the border are equidistant to the optimal situation. Second, it allows for partial compensation of a lower score on one of the indices with a higher score on the other under the restriction that the radial distance to the optimal situation equals the one of reference point A.

A similar reasoning is used to delimit the Exploration category, which includes innovations with scores equal to or lower than the average on the Innovation Management and Innovation Readiness Indicators respectively. Point B in Figure above, constitutes the reference point to construct the circular border. Similarly, partial compensation is allowed but only to the extent that the radial distance of each point on the border to the optimal situation equals the one of point B.

The categories of Commitment and Creation are confined within the borders of the Exploration and Optimisation categories. The line connecting point A and B delimits the Commitment and Creation categories from each other. It is constructed in such a way that the score of the Innovation Management Indicator for innovations in the Commitment category is equal or higher than the score on the Innovation Readiness Indicator. In that sense this category aims to capture innovations that made particular progress in putting concrete market-oriented ideas together.

Given the normal distribution of the sample, each category represents approximately 50 percent (Exploration), 20 percent (Commitment), 20 percent (Creation) and 10 percent (Optimisation) of the innovations.

3.6 SPHINX Innovation context

SPHINX is a 3-year Horizon 2020 project (2019-2021). In particular, SPHINX falls under the category "Research and Innovation Action - RIA", therefore a strong focus on the innovation and scientific advancements should deliver a remarkable result with respect to immediate but also later solution components commercialisation.

In fact, the main aim of SPHINX is making the European Healthcare domain resilient to cyber threats, and that can be trusted by the citizens that provide their personal health records digitally, minimizing costs and risks, while evaluating its replicability to all healthcare domain value chain entities.

Both SPHINX's nature and objective includes a variety of drivers to understand the context Innovation Management, including both internal and external issues along with stakeholders potentially impacting on the project's success.

Drivers and issues include:

- Internal and external opportunities to successfully implement the innovative solutions proposed by SPHINX.
- To reach the goal of successfully implementing the solutions proposed, a strong internal attitude and commitment towards innovation of project partners, coupled with the presence of all capabilities and necessary operational aspects, have been assured since the proposal preparation.
- Among the outputs of Task 1.4, the "Scientific Coordination and Innovation Management" represents the core repository of the main existing innovation management practices and standards, adopted since the beginning of the project and fine-tuned up to the project's end.
- Market, economic/ commercial or political aspects, such as:
 - Adaptation strategies resulting from the policy framework at local, national or international level that cannot be implemented, and
 - The characteristics of the healthcare domain market can affect the innovation adoption, considering that it is fragmented with a conservative attitude towards innovation and a high price elasticity.
- Technical aspects, such as:
 - Depending on real health data to implement the solution or use instead realistic synthetic data
 - The Data model to be used should follow European healthcare principles to be easily adapted to each country specifics
 - Cyber threat categorisation and identification mechanism to be established
 - Replicability, adaptability and elasticity

All these challenges are regularly taken into consideration during the whole project duration, through dedicated tasks foreseen within the management, technical and exploitation activities as foreseen in the SPHINX work plan.

Moreover, the internal stakeholders are mainly project members. SPHINX brings together a multidisciplinary team of 17 European partners including companies, research institutions, universities and end-users both from Information and communication Technology, cybersecurity and healthcare domains. The project's Advisory Board includes additional experts representing both the cybersecurity and healthcare domains which will ensure replicability of the SPHINX solution to the whole healthcare value chain.

Finally, it is important to highlight the common attitude and commitment towards innovation that all the participating actors have. In fact, process and product innovation is the basis of the core business and the main driver for most of them.

3.7 Innovation Strategy Plan and Process

This section details SPHINX's Innovation Strategy Plan and Process. As mentioned earlier, the main goal of the Innovation Strategy Plan and Process is to ensure that the innovation goals of the project do not lose relevance given changing market trends. We achieve this by continuously monitoring the technological and scientific trends and breakthroughs in the market, and by comparing the current trends with the key innovation points mentioned previously.

This is achieved as follows:

- Several deliverables of SPHINX will contain a clearly labelled section which will outline current trends in the area (at the time of writing the deliverable) and clearly state the comparative innovation of the presented technology in relation to current state of the art. This section will be reviewed by the deliverable's reviewers and the Innovation Manager in order to better track the innovation aspects of SPHINX as the project progresses.
- The IM and the Plenary Board (PB) members will continuously monitor the technological trends in order to influence WPs action plans according to the evolving market trends.
- In each plenary meeting, a dedicated session for innovation management will be held. This session will be chaired by the IM in the presence of the WPLs. During the session, each WP leader will present the current innovation status of their WP, in order to acquire feedback from the IM and WPLs.
- During the innovation management session in plenary meetings, the IM and WPLs will re-evaluate the innovation-related risks outlined in Table 2 and assess the overall innovation level of the project or the project's Innovation Health Level (IHL).
- Dissemination plans and the Communication Strategy will be reported well in advance to the IM and PB. The IM, with the support of the Technical Manager (TM), the Exploitation Manager (EP) and the Dissemination & Communication Manager (DCM) need to monitor every dissemination activity in order to ensure that no information that is published can harm the innovative project results.
- If, at any point in time, an innovation-related risk emerges (described in Table 2), the IM will call for an immediate Plenary Board meeting in order to discuss possible measures to mitigate the alleged risk. When necessary, the IM, after consultation with the PB, will call for a re-definition of specific tasks in the corresponding WPs

SPHINX's Innovation Management Process will be assessed three times during the project lifetime, on months 12, 24 and 33.

With the first run (on M12) an initial assessment on the status of the innovations developed in the project will be performed, and an improvement plan will be established and incorporated in the main project plan.

With the second run (on M24) the effect of the execution of the improvement plan will be evaluated and improvement measured, and the plan will be adjusted accordingly.

The last run (on M33) will measure the final innovation status reached, and a final report (which will be reflected in a new updated version of this document) will be produced to be used as a basis for future exploitation.

The Innovation Radar assessment will be carried out using an excel questionnaire, specially prepared to perform all the calculation required to measure the innovation scores and that is based on the work developed by the EURIPIDIS project.

The process is outlined in the following table:

Table 1: Process Outline

STEP #	STEP Description	Owner	Notes
1	Identification of potential innovations that will be developed by the project.	WPL TM IM	This step will be performed only once at 1 st run A maximum of six innovations will be identified
2	IR assessment based on the potential innovations identified.	WPL TM IM	Official IR method to be used.
3	Formal sharing of the assessment results with the partners during the next Plenary meeting. Discussion and identification of improvement areas and improvement actions to be included in the project plan. Each action will be assigned to a specific owner with a specific due date. Evaluation of the effect of the accomplishment of the previous improvement actions on the IR score. Adjustment of the improvement areas and improvement actions previously defined.	PB	The results will be specific values for the Innovation Management and Innovation readiness indicators. Innovation Management and Innovation readiness indicators are expected to improve and reach desired values because of the accomplishment of the actions identified.
4	Execution of the agreed improvement actions.	WPL	Being the actions incorporated in the project plan they will be tracked as per applicable procedures.
5	Final Innovation report describing the most promising innovations that have been developed by the project.	PM TM IM	Conclusions to be incorporated in a report.

Table 2: Description of risks

Description of risk	Impact
State-of-the-art environment/ project objectives lose relevance	High
Technical changes require significant redesign	High
Conflict between innovations produced by the project and existing/ new patents	Low
Results produced by SPHINX are not well exploitable	Medium

The main phases of any management process are depicted in the figure below. It must be stressed however that the innovation process highly depends on aspects such as the type of innovation, the kind of organisation or the internal structure. In the context of innovation projects, for example, some variations could be foreseen.

The different phases of the process are strongly interlinked, as it clearly emerges from the brief description reported here below:

- Phase 1 – Idea Management includes the generation, capturing, evaluation and selection of the new ideas;
- Phase 2 – Development of the innovation project following a dedicated methodology. It is where the implementation of the idea takes place;
- Phase 3 – Market introduction assumes that end-users and lead customers are actively involved since phase 2. Hence, a first reference of an innovative solution (pilot or demonstration) substantially increases the chances of finding additional clients. Therefore, new enabling factors, such as business models, dedicated competences, processes, partners, financing etc. will be required;
- Phase 4 – Innovation results foresees the assessment of the results of the innovation process. These results are measured using financial and non-financial indicators (e.g. revenues, market share, efficiency of process, intangible assets). Assessing the results against these indicators should provide feedback on success and failure and learning opportunities for the further improvement of the innovation management process.

The aim of the proposed Innovation Strategy Plan and Process is to help bridge the well-known “*Valley of Death*” in the commercialization of EU research results, and can only be realized with a holistic Innovation Management, that includes a combined strategy for Intellectual Property management, Data management, and Exploitation and Dissemination of Project Results throughout the lifecycle. The methodology that will be followed will be outlined in several deliverables in WP8.

This methodology foresees specific actions and the order of their implementation, to successfully manage the innovations generated during the project and to ensure the appropriate access to and usage of IPRs before and after the project. All actions will benefit from the competences and experience of the SPHINX partners particularly the industrial partners.

The main set of actions are given below:

- Establishment of the Consortium Agreement (CA). The CA has been agreed and signed by all partners before the start of the project's activities. Besides all provisions necessary for the successful management of the project, the CA includes the partners' responsibilities and liabilities towards each other, a list of relevant background IP for each partner, ownership of Results rules and the access rights for implementation and exploitation, dissemination rules, as well as the consortium budget/pre-financing plan. The partners joint strategy regarding foreground IP protection will be addressed in exploitation agreements that will include licensing arrangements.
- Possible development of an IP Registry including the Results list, relevant background IP, the products list, ownership of Results and Products. Encouragement of partners' participation in webinars/seminars organised by the IPR Helpdesk. IP awareness activities for partners to avoid disclosure of confidential information.
- Carrying out a SWOT analysis and patentability study for SPHINX results to support the decision on how these will be exploited: research wise through dissemination or commercially via filing a patent application. For the second case, dissemination actions will be planned to take place after the patent application. IP strategy development (Task8.5).
- Establishment of a Data Management Plan indicating how Data is shared, released, preserved (D1.3).
- Dissemination Management (Task 8.1, Section 2.2), Dissemination rules & pre-publication review procedures.
- Development of the Dissemination plan and management of Communication activities (Task 8.1)
- Design of the exploitation pathway for the Results (Task 8.2 & Task 8.3), including: i) market analysis ii) innovation delivery plan iii) commercialization plan and actions to ensure future funding resources
- Coordination of individual partner's exploitation plans to avoid conflicts
- Adapting to changes and trends in market and technologies
- Identification of any necessary standards or regulations to establish or take into account (Task 1.2)
- With respect to the dynamic part of the SPHINX, and more specifically the collaboration of partners with external SMEs, a dedicated Task has been foreseen (Task 8.5) that will last for the whole duration of the project. The main goal is to ensure the protection of Intellectual Property of its partners and the external SMEs. This refers to both background and results that will be developed within the SPHINX project.

3.7.1 Innovation Radar Tool

The Innovation Radar Tool is simply an excel providing a set of Questions (we use 16 specific questions and 11 general questions), listed below.

Table 3: Questions related to specific Innovation

Q1	Innovation name
Q2	Is the innovation developed within the project
Q3	Characterise the type of innovation (only to be answered if 2b or 2c is selected)
Q4	If other, please specify

Q5	Characterise the macro type of innovation (only to be answered if "under development" is selected for Q2)
Q6	Will the innovation be introduced to the market or deployed within a partner
Q7	If no exploitation planned, please explain why no exploitation is planned (answer only if 6c is selected)
Q8	Is there a clear owner of the innovation in the consortium or multiple owners
Q9	Indicate who is the "owner" of the innovation
Q10	Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market (answer only if 6a is selected)
Q10.1	Technology transfer
Q10.2	Engagement by Industrial research team of one of their company's business units in project activities
Q10.3	Pilot
Q10.4	Capital investment (VC, Angel, other)
Q10.5	Investment from public authority (national, regional)
Q10.6	Business plan
Q10.7	Prototyping
Q10.8	Market study
Q10.9	Demonstration or Testing activities
Q10.10	Feasibility study
Q10.11	Launch a start-up or spin-off
Q10.12	Other
Q11	If other, please specify
Q12	Indicate (cell A28:A36) which participant(s) (up to a maximum of 3) is/are the key organisation(s) in the project delivering this innovation. For each of these identify under the next question their needs to fulfil their market potential.
Q13	Indicate their needs to fulfil their market potential
Q14	When do you expect that such innovation could be commercialised? (answer only if 6(a) is selected)
Q15	Have any of the project partners... (only to be answered if "Done" or "Planned in Project" is chosen for 10.5 "Investment from public authority")
Q15.a	already applied for support from private investors
Q15.b	already applied for investment from public authorities
Q15.c	Planning to start discussions with private or public investors
Q16	Which partners are in discussion with investors (or are planning such discussions)?

Table 4: General Questions

GQ1	How does the consortium engage end-users?
GQ2	Are there in the consortium internal IPR issues that could compromise the ability of a project partner to exploit new products/solutions/services, internally or in a market place?
GQ3	Please provide specifics of the IPR issues
GQ4	Which are the external bottlenecks that compromise the ability of project partners to exploit new products, solutions or services, internally or in a market place?
GQ4a	IPR
GQ4b	Standards
GQ4c	Regulation
GQ4d	Financing
GQ4e	Workforce's skills

GQ4f	Trade issues (between MS, globally)
GQ4g	Others
GQ5	Indicate how many patents have been applied for by the project
GQ6	Does the review panel consider the project performance in terms of innovation?
GQ7	General observations of innovation expert on this project's innovation performance
GQ8	How would you rate the level of commitment of relevant partners to exploit the innovation?
GQ9	Please indicate the 1 partner (excluding large enterprises) that the panel considers to be the most impressive in terms of innovation potential
GQ10	Please enter some tag words (comma separated) to represent what "innovation elements" are strong in the project
GQ11	Please enter some tag words (comma separated) to represent what "innovation elements" can be improved (or are absent) in the project

The excel provided (assessment questionnaire) automatically calculates the innovation Potential and the Innovators Capacity based on the answers provided using a score table and a method. Once the indicators are calculated for a given innovation, the results are used to evaluate the “Maturity Level” of the innovations assessed.

3.8 Innovation Management Continuous Evaluation

To ensure the suitability, adequacy and effectiveness of the IMS, a dedicated evaluation of the performance should be undertaken, determining specific indicators, methods for monitoring and/ or criteria for evaluating. These criteria should be determined, for example, for the innovation strategy, the deployment of innovation enabling/driving factors and the innovation process and its results. The outputs of this evaluation should include decisions related to the continuous improvement of the IMS. To do so, deviations should be identified and eliminated, leveraging the identified corrective actions in order to improve the efficiency and the results of the IMS. In addition, a roadmap with measures could be defined to eliminate the identified weaknesses as well as to enhance the strengths of the IMS. The implementation of improvement measures should be monitored concerning the timeline, completeness of defined tasks and impact expected on the IMS. Also, to stimulate the learning and continuous improvement within each organisation participating in the SPHINX project, the improvement measures and successes should be communicated to appropriate external interested parties, such as healthcare related organizations, or organizations active in the cybersecurity area.

3.9 Identifying and fostering Innovation enablers / driving factors

The main innovation enabling factors start from the assignments of roles and responsibilities for general innovation management as well as specific innovation task, considering the necessary resources to run the IMS and competences needed. Moreover, other key enablers are awareness, communication, documented information, strategic human resources, IP and knowledge management, and collaboration (internal and external).

All these driving factors are briefly explained here below:

- Roles and responsibilities. They should be clearly and effectively assigned, subcontracting them to external experts for specific tasks where a gap in internal expertise is identified;
- Resources. They are needed for the establishment, implementation, maintenance and continual improvement of the IMS (e.g. human resources, equipment, facilities and budgets);

- Competences. The resources working with innovation activities and the development of them should have the proper competences. In this context, it is also relevant to ensure an improvement of the skills and capabilities of the involved resources, that are essential to enhance the innovation performance;
- Awareness. The importance of innovation should be understood by the resources working with innovation activities, by having clear the innovation vision and strategy together with the importance of their contribution to make the IMS more effective. A strong innovation culture could support this;
- Communication. Internal and external communication relevant to the IMS should be established taking into consideration aspects such as what to communicate, when, to and by whom, together with the provision of communication channels and the intended feedback;
- Collaboration. A defined policy for internal and external collaboration should be elaborated, so that ideas and knowledge could be shared across different persons, groups and units that will be encouraged to collaborate, develop ideas and share knowledge. Here, the involvement of various external actors, called to provide advice upon market related and regulatory topics, can be useful as well;
- Documented information. It should be included in the IMS as it is necessary for the effectiveness of the IMS and represents the evidence of its performance
- Strategic human resources. The IMS should incorporate a strategic approach to human resources that should among others: (i) foster creativity, learning and dissemination of knowledge; (ii) encourage open interactions, trust, diversity and tolerance; (iii) allow persons access to relevant information from management;
- Intellectual property (IP) and knowledge management. On this matter, a policy should be outlined in order to regulate the produced innovation.

3.9.1 Organization of roles and responsibilities

The following figure shows the SPHINX main roles and responsibilities among the Consortium members.

As explained before, within WP1 “Project Management” (led by NTUA as Project Coordinator), a dedicated task (Task 1.4: Scientific Coordination and Innovation Management) is devoted to the innovation management which is led by the partner FINT.

In terms of roles, the partner FINT leads this Task, however SPHINX’s Innovation/Scientific Manager is Dr. Angelos Liapis of KONNEKT-ABLE Technologies Ltd.

In this context, the Scientific and Innovation Manager has the responsibility of governing the innovation management process that is implemented by adopting a hybrid research and innovation methodology. He will iteratively consider the evolution of products and market demands in the addressed sector, the business strategies of the large, small and medium enterprises present in the Consortium, and the results achieved in order to adjust project objectives and requirements, specifying the innovations on which SPHINX should focus more and identifying exploitation potentials.

The Innovation Manager is part of the SPHINX Plenary Board, as the following figure shows.

The Plenary Board is chaired by the Project Coordinator and also composed by the WP leaders, the Innovation/Scientific Manager and Exploitation Manager. This team has to ensure that the project follows the expected planning, timing and budget at all levels. This Committee will meet on a 6-months basis, and whenever it is considered necessary due to extraordinary situations that might take place during the course of the project.

To effectively undertake its role and responsibility, the Scientific and Innovation Manager will work in contact with, and need the strong commitment of the three involved end-users (Polaris Medical, HES and DYPE5). At the same time, he will also deal with the Advisory Board, that includes experts representing organizations from multiple sectors, which will ensure replicability of the tool to other sectors (mainly those considered critical infrastructures), and therefore its potential commercialisation to the mentioned sectors beyond the life time of the project.

3.9.2 Resources and competences

As widely explained, all SPHINX partners provide the necessary range of **resources, expertise, competence and operational capacity** to deliver the innovative project objectives.

In this sense, a detailed description of each partner, its key persons (including those involved in innovation management), resources (e.g. human resources, equipment, facilities and budget) and competences (e.g. publications, relevant products, projects or activities) is provided in the SPHINX proposal. According to this description, it is evident that they ensure the overall SPHINX innovation performance. In fact, the equilibrium between industrial and research partners, together with the demonstrated expertise of them, guarantees that the project innovates and fully delivers on the proposed services and products, achieving all objectives with high impact. Further, the high number of industrial partners assures a real orientation towards future business exploitation of the project results.

In addition to that, to guarantee the success of the proposed innovation, SPHINX's partner structure has been designed to work on three pilot sites located in Europe (Romania, Portugal and Greece). Each of the core pilot sites will be composed of:

- 1 End-User (healthcare provider), acting as end user and co-designer of the SPHINX solution; and
- 1 Research entity (research centre, university or SME), working together with the end-user in order to supply the required cybersecurity technical know-how to implement the SPHINX's solution, based on the information technology (IT) infrastructure of the end-user. Every Research entity is located in the same country of the end-user, being geographically close to enable close cooperation in a daily basis.

In this sense, the clusters composed for each pilot-site include the needed resources and competences and provide a positive synergy among all Consortium partners, creating an ecosystem for innovation in cybersecurity in health care.

3.9.3 Communication, Awareness and Collaboration

Within SPHINX, communication, awareness and collaboration represent key elements for the overall project success. It is important to highlight that, in this context, these concepts are intrinsically connected and tend to overlap. For this reason, they are discussed together.

Communication, awareness and collaboration actions have been foreseen on two levels: internal and external. These actions aim to maximise the knowledge sharing and present the results of the innovation process within and beyond the Consortium.

Starting in the internal level, SPHINX possesses a well-defined structure especially created to maintain a fluid and thorough communication among the partners, with a view to obtain the most efficient collaboration and increase the synergy for the sake of the quality of results. The main channel of the communication structure is the Project Coordinator, who receives or prepares the information of different nature (reports, minutes, publications, patents and licensing processes) and is responsible of conveying this information to the rest of partners. To do that, the Coordinator uses different means, such as:

- A collaborative Alfresco website (<https://alfresco.epu.ntua.gr/>) to facilitate the coordination between partners and the sharing of relevant information. The collaborative tools include services such as: shared documents, shared calendar, news publication, tasks and issues tracking, risk management, Wiki pages for sharing knowledge, discussion forums, follow-up commercial opportunities.
- Regularly e-meetings / conference calls to keep the partners updated on the on-going status of the WPs in order to monitor and share the progress and the quality of major project outputs. They are plenary e-meetings involving all the Consortium partners or dedicated conference calls devoted to specific WPs;

- Focus groups (organised together with the Innovation Manager) and regular e-meetings, involving the end-users and the Advisory Board members to regularly collect their feedback and update them on project achievements;
- Annual AB workshops that take place in parallel with the annual general meetings (every year these are celebrated in a different end-user premises), which allow aligning the developed work with stakeholders' interests and feedbacks.

Moving to the external level, SPHINX will “promote the research and innovation action and its results” through two distinct but complementary approaches:

- Communication and Dissemination strategy and actions which are detailed in the ‘T8.1 - Dissemination activities (D8.2: Dissemination Plan). The plan gives an overview on the dissemination activities to be carried out by the SPHINX Consortium to disclose and give public access to the progress and results of the project. It defines the dissemination objectives, key messages, target audiences, as well as specific objectives for each identified target group. In addition, D8.2 identifies the targeted communication channels to be used, promotional materials, as well as the training workshops with details on the financial and human resources and timing. SPHINX has a special focus on end-users' engagement and stakeholders' involvement during all project phases; and
- Exploitation, given the moderate Technology Readiness Level (TRL) level to be achieved, the strong innovation potential of the SPHINX solution, coupled with a predominant presence of innovative SMEs within the Consortium, a preliminary business plan together with a business model and a market assessment are included as exploitation strategies.

All these actions are carried out in the frame of WP8 “Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation” led by ViLabs, with the support of all partners. A detailed description of the individual and common exploitation plans will be described at D8.4: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v1 (due at M12).

This WP has a list of clear objectives:

- Increase the global visibility of the SPHINX project and its outcomes in Europe and beyond;
- Raise the awareness of the target groups and potential users about SPHINX; understand what it can deliver and how it relates to their needs;
- Place the SPHINX toolkit among the top of the EU cyber security related innovations;
- Exchange the information and results on national and regional activities and agendas to contribute in developing related initiatives and projects;
- Enhance European and global market uptake of the SPHINX toolkit.

Within WP8, different channels / tools / materials are used to realize these objectives. They mainly reflect the nature of the objectives presented above:

- Dissemination channels, especially the SPHINX official website and social media, participation to dedicated events, the creation of promotional material, the organisation of workshops at demonstration sites targeting hospitals and health care companies, advisory board members, policy-makers, legislation bodies, and articles in online and printed magazines;
- Exploitation tools, such as the SPHINX business plan and roadmap and the analysis of the replicability and EU funding mechanisms for further deployment; and
- Communication material, e.g. brochures, posters and rollups, press releases, newsletters and five (5) videos.

This overall structure will allow to reach key audiences with the main messages relevant to promote the research and innovation action and its result and to foster a continuous internal and external collaboration.

3.9.4 Documented Information

In order to provide evidence of performance and the effectiveness of the actions foreseen by the SPHINX Consortium, all the outcomes of the meetings, workshops and conference calls have been made traceable thanks to dedicated Minutes of Meeting (MoM), providing a brief summary with the main outcomes and expected next steps. Actions Points from each meeting are assigned to partners with the agreed deadlines, in order to improve traceability and keep all partners informed about the course of the project.

Furthermore, thanks to SPHINX's collaborative communication tool, all the documents and WP related information are uploaded, shared, stored and protected, granting access to the involved Consortium partners.

All in all, this Innovation Management Plan provides a high-level guidance on establishing and maintaining an innovation management system (IMS) during the whole project.

3.10 Standardisation

The SPHINX project will enforce the use of relevant standards and open source projects, and will try to contribute in their improvement when possible, in order to strengthen the strategic position of the industrial partners. Special emphasis will be made during the project in taking part in one or more of the following standardisation organisations: IoT-GSI ([Internet of Things Global Standards Initiative](#)), IEEE-SA (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standards Association /Internet of Things Working Group), OMG (Object Management Group). These organisations focus on extending the advanced capabilities of IoT to new commercial applications. The inter-component communication in the SPHINX platform will align with the relevant standards of open interfaces and interoperability and contribute to the harmonization of related means and procedures for wearable medical devices.

It will be necessary to make an inventory of the formal and informal prediction, prevention, response and mitigation standards with respect to clinical/ health critical infrastructure security and protection as well as the existing ontologies in the different partner countries. The pilots can provide valuable information about which standards are working, which standards need improvement and which standards need to be developed. A first impact will be the representation of SPHINX findings within the relevant standardization groups with the aim of refining the standards and suggesting new versions based on SPHINX needs. SPHINX will pay particular attention to the **EU Cybersecurity Act**, adopted a few weeks ago, which **establishes a European cybersecurity certification framework for ICT products, services and processes**. Standardisation will play an important role in the new framework. **The Cybersecurity Act entered into force starting May 2019.**

A very important issue is the standardization of measurements in order to achieve interoperability and enable interchange of data between various systems. We will rely on W3C work in the standardization of the description of the sensor information, like SSN ontology. It is important to rely on open standards and specifications for the collected data as well. The most important initiative is Big data reference standards (<http://bigdatawg.nist.gov/home.php>). This is a kind of broad agreement among commercial, academic, and government leaders about the remarkable potential of "Big Data" to spark innovation, fuel commerce, and drive progress. Furthermore, European Big Data Alliance (<http://www.bdva.eu/>) will be another critical standardisation activity that SPHINX will also closely follow and potentially contribute.

3.11 IPR Management

For the success of the project, it is essential that all project partners agree on explicit rules concerning intellectual property rights (IPR) ownership, access rights to any Background and Foreground IP for the execution of the project and the protection of IPR and confidential information. The basic principles are defined and summarised in the section below.

The industrial partners of SPHINX will especially exploit SPHINX's results and developments within their portfolio. Although SPHINX will be as close to the real life as possible, the requirements for a professional and complete product are mostly higher than for an application or implementation in a project such as SPHINX. Especially in terms of design of each module of the toolkit, the demands are much higher for targeted consumers. Hence, the affected industrial consortium members, particularly FINT, KT, SIVCO, AiDEAS, PDMFC, EDGE and TEC, as well as Research and Development partners that are also licensing technologies have a strong interest to invest time and money on their own to bridge the gap between project and the earliest possible exploitation. Depending on the particular development and success during the project, individual actions are planned and described in the individual exploitation plans of the consortium members in Section 4.11

The IPR management of SPHINX will be coordinated by VUB-LSTS which will include coordination of all IPR-related activities. VUB-LSTS will be the point of contact for all communication with officials and administration in connection to IPR. The establishment of intellectual property and other aspects of innovation in this project will primarily be done by the respective work packages.

Participants plan to jointly or individually prepare patent applications for new concepts and solutions conceived, respectively jointly by one or more participant or solely by one participant. SPHINX aims to have patents filed by one or more partners to protect innovations from the project which have the potential to have a significant impact.

Innovations, concepts and solutions that will not be protected by patent applications by the participants will be made public after agreement between the partners and per the procedure established in the Consortium Agreement, in order to prevent others from blocking usage of these results. Further, the use of the IPR Helpdesk (<https://iprhelpdesk.eu/>) will be promoted to help individual participants and partners with questions related to the protection of IPR.

A procedure has been established to inform all other partners in the project when results of the project will be made public (e.g. in a conference paper). This allows partners to protect their IPR before publication, without which would make it that impossible. VUB-LSTS will maintain a record of all related documents and discussions. This could later be used as a base for resolving conflicts related to IPR filings. These procedures ensure that intellectual property will be secured in the interest of project partners.

In order to ensure a smooth execution of the project, the project partners agreed to grant each other royalty-free Access Rights to their Background and Foreground IP for the execution of the project. The Consortium Agreement further details the Access Rights during and after the project to Background and Foreground IP.

The full details of the legal framework for the project related to the work, IP Ownership, Access Rights to Background and Foreground IP for the duration of the project and any other matters of the consortium's interest has been defined in the Consortium Agreement and will fully described in D8.1 (SPHINX IPR Plan & IPR Management) due on M9.

In line with the above outlined strategy, each partner will be involved in exploitation activities according to their expertise. The individual exploitation plans of SPHINX consortium members are listed below.

3.12 Consortium members' exploitation plans

3.12.1 National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)

As public institution of higher education NTUA is a non-profit organization that will not perform commercial exploitation of the project's results. Nevertheless, NTUA will have significant benefits to reap from the project results that we outline below. The project's team will incorporate material and research results of the project in related courses in the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, perform seminars and further train

undergraduate students as part of their final year projects. Postgraduate students attending the MSc in Techno-economic students will also benefit from similar inclusion of the project's results in courses, projects and seminars. Additionally, PhD theses will be drawn out based either directly or indirectly from the project's results in the areas of NTUA's scientific contributions to the project, from members of the project's team, as well as new PhD candidates. These candidates along with the senior researchers and faculty members intend to further their expertise in the fields of cybersecurity in the health sector, cybersecurity in general, information security standardisation and implementation of standards. This expertise will be used to publish research papers, attend and present work in conferences, and allow the participation of NTUA in other closely or loosely related research projects.

3.12.2 Future Intelligence Ltd (FINT)

Future Intelligence Ltd is a European SME company specializing in Information & Communication Technologies (ICT). It aims at providing high-demanded solutions and business services covering a number of activities such as wireless communications, networking and cloud computing. At the same time, it offers consulting services to other businesses and organizations which are willing to use IT and telecommunications as a lever in order to enhance their productivity and operation procedures. The company's main goal is to contribute to scientific research on the fields mentioned above by pitching in with other players in order to produce innovative and original products or services.

FINT is one of the leading IoT devices manufacturers and IoT Platform Providers in Europe. The company's objective is to build an IoT enabled ecosystem which can expand horizontally and vertically providing a playground for vendors, OEMs and programmers. One of the main pillars is Cyber security in which FINT provides accelerated security services through its accelerated Gateways. Through SPHINX project FINT expects to extend its cyber security services portfolio by adding to its suite Honeypots and more enhanced services (Knowledge Base for Cyber Security Incidents) for Health sector.

More specifically FINT's consider Health sector as one of the Vertical applications within Smart Cities environment and along with Cyber Security department will focus on exploiting dedicated cyber security services for hospitals and health care IoT infrastructure (health devices, along with Hospital Infrastructure, energy monitoring and management etc) within its FINoT platform.

3.12.3 KONNEKTABLE Technologies Ltd (KT)

Konnekt-able Technologies is a technology research and development firm, based in the Republic of Ireland. Our vision is simple – to create connections – through technology, through the practical application of research, and through collaboration. Konnekt-able's principals have extensive experience in research work and in following that work through to the commercial marketplace.

Konnekt-able's Software Engineers, Analysts and Programmers keep abreast of all major technology innovations and developments that can add value to our business activities. We are using a series of development platforms, chosen on the basis of their suitability, adaptability, scalability and flexibility, to successfully design and implement custom-built solutions, which meet complex customer requirements under strict Service Level Agreements where applicable.

The overall aim of Konnekt-able Technologies Ltd. is to exploit the results of SPHINX project as part of its core strategy in the marketing and selling of industrial projects and services. Through its participation in SPHINX and other European projects, KT strengthens its core business value which is enabling the users and creating connections utilizing technological solutions and data-driven insights. The practical application of research and the acquired knowledge will be incorporated to the business department, increasing its capabilities and the

possibility of offering enhanced products and services during the project, with the aim of strengthening cyber security for health care, critical infrastructures and production lines; propelling an increasingly massive deployment of cyber security solutions and an increasingly intense use of those solutions in their respective fields. The results will strengthen KT's competence and will be transferred into industrial use via contract R&D projects and consultancy services and as plug-ins to the commercial platforms of the company. Furthermore, results that are not of commercial TRL will be exploited in current and forthcoming European R&D projects.

Specifically speaking, the topics and domains of SPHINX that KT seeks to share and gain knowledge are mostly focussed on data management, data exchange and knowledge discovery technologies, service based architectures, IoT based services management and knowledge discovery through AI-enabled Decision Support Systems and Machine learning technology, with the aim of verifying the possibility to capitalise on both knowledge and technology and expand further its current commercial portfolio and business activities as these are displayed in the company's website <http://konnekt-able.com/>.

Furthermore, KT will actively contribute to the overall Business activities of SPHINX: Technology itself is just a few interesting results if the business orientation is not considered. In this path the technologies are valorised, the risks are mitigated, the exploitation strategy is defined and, finally, a business plan is produced. The business activity path ends with a "mixed" activity, partially technological, focused on the commercialisation of the technology which is one of the core objectives of the company.

KT is a SME which means making profit is part of the process that keeps the enterprise up and running, but profit is a term that can take several meanings. Releasing a free, community version, of a software that will enable more users and facilitate their processes must also be viewed as profit, profit for society and its members. Not all profit can be measured in terms of revenue. Therefore, KT is proud of participating in European projects that, by definition, aim at enhancing the quality of life of its citizens, and proud of embracing Open Science protocols and procedures.

3.12.4 ViLabs LTD (ViLabs)

VILABS's contribution to the SPHINX project is concentrated mainly on knowledge development in Cybersecurity and assessing the potential roll-out of the SPHINX solution and its components. The knowledge that SPHINX will gain on the trends and influencing factors in Cybersecurity in Health sector, will contribute to the understanding of security within and beyond the project. This knowledge will be shared within the project consortium and VILABS spreads this knowledge to the national and international stakeholders (Industry (Security and IoT), medical organisations, research, policy, society, international networks and relevant projects. VILABS analyses also the market and develops the business plan of the final SPHINX solution. VILABS is willing to sustain the solution and collaborate with one or more project partners to exploit it further to enter at the real market. Furthermore, VILABS will use existing project networks to contribute to the distribution of the SPHINX ideas among actors all over Europe.

3.12.5 SIVECO Romania SA (SIVECO)

SIVECO, as an IT leading company, will use SPHINX results to develop new business models and to attract clients from healthcare domain. SIVECO will use its business network to exploit SPHINX results by presenting the developments to the different lines of business inside the company and in dedicated events.

The team engaged in the collaborative development of SPHINX concept will be exposed to a huge amount of knowledge and know-how. SIVECO aims at playing a key role in the definition, development and deployment of SPHINX's Advanced Visualization Dashboards. SIVECO's commercial interest is in customizing the SPHINX Advanced Visualization Dashboards for different business cases and in fostering the replicability of the solution for new clients.

3.12.6 AIDEAS OÜ (AiDEAS)

AiDEAS's main interests lie in the link between product development and the continuous product/ process/ services innovation taking place in health care industry. They will exploit the knowledge gained, especially for the development of machine learning algorithms for anomaly intrusion detection. AiDEAS expects to increase its participation in joint projects related to cyber security technologies. In particular, AiDEAS expects to become a reference partner for the provision of AI services in cyber security technologies in health care sector, a key future industry target, according to all the available forecasts. Participation in projects like SPHINX will also bring AiDEAS the opportunity to get a clearer picture of the technology status and evolution at the standardisation level, so future decisions can be made for the development and improvement of new AiDEAS algorithms. In addition, the intrusion detection algorithms using honeypot data developed in SPHINX can be generalized and modified for a multiple of other scenarios.

3.12.7 Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU) (formally named Technological Educational Institute of Crete (TEIC))

TEIC expects to exploit the outcomes of the project by promoting their use within established communities. Our main aim is to enable technology transfer to existing communications networks that provide privacy and security properties. A consequence of this emphasis on VAaaS and the Cyber Security Toolbox has generated interest within the research community to progress the state-of-the-art in this area, with at least one project. The project can benefit from this push in the state-of-the-art since the results of this effort are open-sourced and licensed according to the same legal regime as the one the project uses. We are also aware of other contemporary research activity around Cyber Security tools. These proposals are the current state-of-the-art with respect to scalability, robustness and latency; however, they do not represent significant advances in terms of deployability and accessibility. It will be our aim to leverage research findings from these proposals to further enhance our own product. With regards to our educational activities, Sphinx will provide new topics and new motivations to the Privacy and Cyber security Technologies course. The aim to make SPHINX widely used, and the techniques that both the academic and the industry partners will research to solve real world problems, will increase the interest of potential new researchers in the project. From the new academic year, the Cyber Security Technologies course will introduce several of the research topics that SPHINX tackles, effectively updating the material that elaborate on mix networks as a solution to problems requiring cyber security in Health care.

3.12.8 Projecto Desenvolvimento Manutenção Formação e Consultadoria (PDMFC)

The experience and know-how to be gained during the SPHINX project will allow PDMFC to enhance our current versions of the Sandbox and SIEM tools. Both are based on Open Source technologies and their new versions will be based largely on Open Source as well. Therefore, PDMFC will maintain its commitment to this movement and contribute to the further development of these technologies. We will work towards becoming a Conformity Assessment Body in order to issue CyberSecurity Certifications at the EU level (as a result of the application of the EU Cybersecurity Act) using the tools to be partially developed within the scope of SPHINX.

And of course our participation in the SPHINX's project will project our name and reputation beyond the lifetime of the project and they possibility to pilot our solutions in real environments, will significantly increase our market penetration in the area of cybersecurity consulting and as a solution integrator.

3.12.9 EDGENEERING (EDGE)

The security technology developed and experience gained through the SPHINX project will be funnelled into EDGE's smart devices and eCare Platform services, adding relevant improvements to the company's trusted security practices. EDGE's market competitiveness will also benefit from the verification of the new security technologies' usability and incorporation in its eCare devices and commodity cloud platform. Further, the project will also provide valuable insight on the novel security techniques and technologies to bridge the existing gaps in IoT devices' security and protection. As an emerging SME, the reputation gained by EDGE from the SPHINX project will positively influence its future business development and sales activities, namely in Portugal, Portuguese-spoken countries and Europe.

3.12.10 Tech Inspire Ltd (TEC)

TEC Exploitation Plan provides an overview of the strategies and actions needed for the adoption and exploitation of the Homomorphic Encryption Solution generated by the SPHINX project. It provides the framework for identifying, developing and optimizing TEC Security Solution at large for the exploitation of project results during the project and after its completion. The core strategy is based on using the extensive contact network of each consortium members as a starting point to get in touch with new potential users of the project solutions. In addition, TEC marketing team has worked closely with UK and European industries to integrate our homomorphic encryption based searchable solutions as part of Cloud offering of major health care providers. These existing channels will be exploited to seek any potential new business opportunities in the European cyber security market place.

3.12.11 Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Research Group on Law, Science, Technology & Society (VUB-LSTS)

The motivation of VUB-LSTS for the participation in the SPHINX project is the intrinsic interest to promote privacy, data protection and security in the emerging innovative solutions and the keenness to identify and facilitate the mitigation of data protection threats and risks. Apart from the unique opportunity to enhance and adapt the EU cybersecurity and personal data protection legal framework, VUB will not only monitor legal compliance with the European legal framework but will contribute to Privacy-and Security-by-Design solutions and upgrade its know-how. Accordingly, VUB-LSTS has recently launched a new research law with a particular emphasis on cybersecurity and data security, the Cyber and Data Security Lab (CDSL, <https://cdsl.research.vub.be>). At the same time, VUB-LSTS continues its research and academic activities along the lines of international, peer-reviewed publications and conferences. Consequently, VUB-LSTS exploitation plan will in particular focus on these two thematic areas: Strengthening CDSL through the acquisition of valuable know-how and insight and also exposure in the cybersecurity community; And, also, through organisation of scientific publication(s) in international peer reviewed law journals, and presence in our annual data privacy and information security conference, CPDP (<https://www.cpdpconferences.org>).

3.12.12 Fundación Tecnalia Research & Innovation (TECNALIA)

TECNALIA is a non-profit educational and research organisation and in line with its aims does not aim to generate profit. The SPHINX outcomes, particularly those leading to high-quality and high-impact publications by TECNALIA staff. Moreover, participating in such an important project as SPHINX helps to obtain next EU funding. Work in SPHINX is actively contributing to increasing TECNALIA's capacity around two key areas:

- (1) privacy-enhancing technologies relating to cryptographic and networking technologies, and
- (2) privacy-enhancing technologies relating to statistical techniques and machine learning.

This capacity, and the track record of excellence will be used in the future for accessing a number of funding opportunities: further grants on requiring expertise on those topics, as well as maintaining TECNALIA's status as a Research Centre of Excellence in Cyber Security. TECNALIA's expertise in Privacy Enhancing Technologies and the SPHINX project already allowed us to obtain a new funding for the EU H2020 project. Thanks to the involvement into SPHINX project and privacy-enhancing technologies

TECNALIA is also now a Centre for cybersecurity teaching excellence. Resources associated with SPHINX are already being supplemented by other grants (from the EPSRC) to deliver better solutions and analysis. In this sense we will further extend the portfolio of the centre to offer the SPHINX solutions.

In this direction TECNALIA host one of the first Blockchain laboratories in SPAIN and will use the Blockchain Threat Registry as a core asset to enhance the services offered in the Blockchain laboratory. The main aim of the Blockchain Laboratory is to help companies in the conceptualisation and deployment of Blockchain solutions addressing business needs of these organisations.

3.12.13 Intracom S.A. Telecom Solutions (ICOM)

Many results of the SPHINX project can be exploited by ICOM. As responsible partner for the overall architecture and of its implementation as a Common Integration Platform, ICOM will have a deep knowledge of the wide variety of technologies that SPHINX is inheriting from previous projects and that are being customised, integrated, extended to address emerging needs coming from Health care and relevant stakeholders. Also, intangible results will be exploited: market analysis, stakeholders' needs, new business models mapped onto the European framework of regulation will be for ICOM an opportunity to extend the health care business area also outside national frontiers.

ICOM is a very active player in the ICT domain. In this regard, the ICOM is fully involved in delivering effective ICT solutions in several markets. However, ICOM has also a long and solid experience in national and European co-funded research projects, tailored for the Cyber Security. Hence the approach to exploitation will be twofold: a new and more competitive IT service and solutions offering to the Cyber Security market in which ICOM already supplies many big customers a deeper knowledge of the more recent technologies for the Health care sector to be exploited in even more challenging research initiatives. Indeed, expertise and skills developed inside the project will increase the already important knowledge and know-how of the involved team giving ICOM the chance to profitably continue its research activity in European projects in the Cyber Security and Health care domain.

3.12.14 Imprensa Nacional-Casa da Moeda (INCM)

INCM will leverage project results to complement its original market positioning with innovative sandbox and cybersecurity certification services. In collaboration with healthcare and technical partners, INCM will help to identify the health care cyber security trends and based on that contribute to define reference scenarios and real life test cases. These activities will help INCM to enhance the innovation capacity and integration of SPHINX knowledge and results in its strategic focus areas. Due to its role in security services, INCM is definitely committed to the SPHINX project with respect to the utilisation of the cyber security solutions developed throughout the project, both for other demonstration/ innovation actions and/ or for research purposes. However, in case of large scale deployment, these solutions have to meet a number of key criteria, regarding economic and security issues, not jeopardizing the security of health care infrastructure. The complexity of the network architecture suitable for mass heterogeneous health care equipment needs to accommodate the necessary security operations systems and capabilities of integration with existing IT and security systems. Moreover, for the certification and consequent route to the market is complex and the availability of suitable elements for deployment is probably the most difficult issue, due to the fact that the developed health care cybersecurity solution will be applied in personal and health related records.

3.12.15 Polaris Medical clinică de tratament și recuperare SA (Polaris Medical)

During the SPHINX project, Polaris Medical clinică de tratament și recuperare SA (Polaris Medical) will implement pilots testing of the developed cyber security health care services and tools. As a result, a new kind cyber security for Health care providers will be developed and tested. This new cyber security solution may stay in use in the Polaris Medical also after the piloting period and the project lifetime. During the project, the piloted cyber security method will be offered to different modules, medical devices etc. In the future, the plan is to extend the same solution to all infrastructure of the hospital. Through this development, it can be stated that the project results are well sustained and further developed within Polaris Medical. For example, the data secure correspondence between health care professionals and patients through the electronic health care service portal, the new cyber secure exchange of health and personal records, which will all be part of the pilot, we aim at remaining as usual activities in the hospital infrastructure.

3.12.16 Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (HES)

During the SPHINX project, Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (HES) will implement a pilot activity to test and validate the developed SPHINX cyber security services and tools. The new SPHINX cyber security solution may stay in use in the HES after the project's lifetime and, based on the pilot results, HES will consider the adoption of SPHINX best cybersecurity practices, namely to reinforce the security training of its professionals and the security policies implemented with respect to connected medical devices and the patients' information.

3.12.17 5 Ygionomiki Periferia Thessalias & Stereas Elladas (DYPE5)

5 YGEIONOMIKI PERIFERIA THESSALIAS & STEREAS ELLADAS (DYPE5) is coordinating WP7 and all piloting actions. Two large Greek Public Hospitals, University Hospital of Larissa (tertiary healthcare) and General Hospital of Volos (secondary healthcare), along with Portugal's HESE and Romania's Polaris Medical comprise the testbed where scenarios and test cases will be defined to validate the SPHINX Ecosystem's functionality. The Greek Health IT landscape is currently undergoing a major transformation and cyber-security policies and actions operate still on a relatively low level of adherence. SPHINX will provide the opportunity to incorporate an innovative basket of smart solutions into the pilots' complex environments, driving DYPE5 to gain on new experiences, such as:

- Smart safeguarding DYPE5's assets, systems and information exchange
- Raising awareness and educating the hospitals' personnel on cyber-security issues and actions
- Developing a knowledge repository containing piloting/project coordination methodology, organizational/technical procedures and technology assets
- Laying the foundation to plan and develop a Regional cyber-security policy scheme

DYPE5 plans to capitalize on these gains by:

- formulating cyber-security policies and regulations to apply to all Health Organizations under its scope of management (13 Hospitals and 65 Primary Care Centres – almost 10.000 professionals)
- rolling out best practices and SPHINX Ecosystem technology components to other DYPE5's healthcare establishments
- Committing SPHINX results and findings to the Greek Ministry's National Health Cyber-Security Policy
- Establishing a scientific and technological repository of knowledge for future cyber-security developments

3.13 Outcomes from the SPHINX Innovation MGT Phases

3.13.1 Exploration phase

True innovation should always start with the customer in mind, in our case this is the broader healthcare sector and the challenges that it faces as it transitions from paper to digital record-keeping, through the advancements of technology and the Internet. The Exploration phase includes three primary steps:

- Get customer insight
- Identify the problem
- Identify jobs to be done

Get customer insight: As the healthcare industry moves to adopt new technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), wireless and networked medical devices, in addition to mobile and web-based applications, it has fallen behind in ensuring the security of electronic protected health information (e-PHI) and as a consequence, to ensure patients' rights in terms of Data Privacy. Equally worrying, clinical systems and medical devices have historically not been designed around any Cybersecurity framework that enforces Privacy and Security by design, leading to an increased opportunity for technology savvy criminals to exploit them for fun and/or profit, with potentially catastrophic consequences to patients (David Arney, 2011). Using systems, the way they were designed, often causes gaps in security. With the increased value of medical information, organizations need to find ways to properly assess vendors and devices before installing and deploying them within their organizations. (David Arney, 2011) examines the regulations, such as The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996, and security features of networked medical devices by identifying security requirements, the principal threats and the challenges involved in addressing them, focusing not only on attack models, but also on a model for networked medical devices. A patient's privacy and safety may be jeopardized due to inadequate security that would enable malicious attacks using malware to compromise patient information or even worse cause physical harm (David Arney, 2011).

Identify the problem: Traditionally, medical devices have been used in a stand-alone mode or have had limited network connectivity, typically to a proprietary subnet of similar devices (e.g., a patient monitoring network). However, economic pressures, the increasing use of IT, and the desire to improve staff efficiency and quality of care have led to a usage model where more devices are integrated with the larger hospital IT infrastructure. Attractive price points and lower maintenance costs make standard Internet protocol (IP) networks the technology of choice. Similarly, device manufacturers increasingly utilize commercial technologies, standard operating systems, or other off-the-shelf software components, as well as commercial central processing unit (CPU) platforms (Wirth, 2011). Although the economic benefit of this approach is clear, it has introduced vulnerabilities and is exposing medical devices to common cyber threats. Additionally, a device's proprietary software denies access for the organisation, to add security measures to the device. As medical devices incorporate more information technologies for added features, the complexity of critical devices may affect the safety of the patient and or the device. In the US, Healthcare organizations receive a Manufacturer Disclosure Statement for Medical Device Security (MDS2) that provides security related information regarding the security features that are supported (Keller, 2017). However, the device may not support encryption, anti-virus, or account credentials. Another issue is that the typical life cycle of the device is longer than the life cycle of the operating system. Due to the regulatory compliance and validations that manufacturers must follow, these operating systems can no longer be patched (Wirth, 2011). Similarly, the European Union enacted the Medical

Device Regulation of 2017 (Regulation (EU) 2017/745)) which applies to every manufacturer, authorized representative, importer or distributor of medical devices, regulatory affairs or quality management professional.

Identify jobs to be done: While regulatory compliance standards are already being met by the manufacturers, there may still be gaps between the medical device security and the policies and or procedures of the healthcare facility. So how then does the healthcare sector go about assessing the risk or lack of security to protect patient's information that may or may not be stored on the physical device?

3.13.1.1 SCAMPER method

Through the exploration of the three points described above the goal is to gain new insights and information to further build out the initial idea set during the proposal implementation phase. To better facilitate this process, we have applied the **SCAMPER**¹ method. **SCAMPER** is an acronym that is used to help prompt creative ideas for improving existing products or services or creating new innovations. The letters in **SCAMPER** stand for substitute, combine, adapt, modify, put to another use, eliminate, and reverse. Each letter is associated with a string of questions that can be asked about existing products to discover methods of improvement or entirely new opportunities. The **SCAMPER** template of **SPHINX** can be accessed through the following link:

<https://forms.gle/FaERCRzCSD519eVo9>

3.13.1.1.1 SPHINX SCAMPER Consolidated Results

Regarding the **Substitute** question the majority of the partners indicated that their developed SPHINX solution aims to be used for substituting the solutions utilised today in the health sector by offering new features or enhancing existing ones; for example by utilising AI paradigm to automate processes, new forms of encryption to fulfil GDPR privacy requirements etc. For the **Combine**, the collected answers indicated that SPHINX may be used in a synergistic/complementary way with third party solutions and vendors; further to that other answers indicated the need to combine SPHINX components towards providing holistic Cybersecurity solutions. The answers in the **Adapt** question indicated that the SPHINX solution should adapt their building frameworks and technologies to accommodate automation, use of AI and interoperability with third party (open source mainly) tools and solutions. As far as the **Modify** is concerned, the direction was on extending SPHINX's scope to provide a holistic Cybersecurity solution (central command and control) by being able to track, monitor and control each device operating in the health organisation and by being able to cope with the sudden increases in the work load. Regarding the "**Put on another use**", the answers clearly showed that SPHINX could be adapted and used in other vectors like finances and transportation domains. The answers in the **Eliminate** question highlighted the need to reduce further manual operation and activities and minimise complexity in the setup, deployment and configuration operations. Finally, in the **Reverse** the provided answers indicated that the use of mature and well proven existing standards and technologies for designing SPHINX tools would bring SPHINX closer to the market but farther from its research objectives; moreover it was suggested to abandon flat networking in favour of a total virtualised solution so that networks and devices could be naturally sandboxed and have an extra layer of protection against cyberattack.

3.13.1.1.2 Scamper Responses

This section highlights the partners' contribution in the respective questionnaire and presents their raw answers that were used for deriving the consolidated and key results discussed in the above and below sections.

¹ <https://www.designorate.com/a-guide-to-the-scamper-technique-for-creative-thinking/>

Figure 5: Partners' contribution in SCAMPER Response

SPHINX Partner	Substitute	Combine	Adopt	Modify	Put to Another Use	Eliminate	Reverse
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Sphinx can replace the offline risk analysis performed for ISMSs with an active, online and almost real-time one.	Collaborations with ICT and equipment vendors for hospitals can integrate security requirements with technical specifications of networks, hardware and software that exist in hospitals, to cover security concerns that may slip through the cracks, for example if a security requirement, like encryption, is always expected to be fulfilled by another party.	Some tools and components of SPHINX may be supplied independently to cater for individual needs or operational environments.	SPHINX could be integrated as a single software solution when further developed.	SPHINX can be used with few modifications for other organisations of similar scale as hospitals.	The simulated environment is necessary only for initial tests. Once SPHINX has been integrated in an operational environment, the simulations won't be necessary.	Regarding the certification aspect of SPHINX, the tools could have been designed and chosen to satisfy existing standards, rather than to perform research that may improve them. This would have brought SPHINX closer to the market, but at the same time away from its research goals.
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E	Sphinx could replace cloud based SIEMs and other expensive solutions with a on premises	Nothing is an island in security, integration with existing security tools such as firewalls, routers, ids, ips, wafs, end	Existing log repositories, or network packet captures, forensic datalakes could be adapted to be worked upon	If the scope could be magically extended to support and track every device inside an hospital, Sphinx could	Make Sphinx the access control solution for humans and devices alike, everything that moves would	It could eliminate existing hand rolled solutions for security monitoring and replace it with a common	Instead of the flat networks that are the most common, everything could be virtualized and orchestrated by

SPHINX Partner	Substitute	Combine	Adopt	Modify	Put to Another Use	Eliminate	Reverse
CONSULTAD ORIALDA, Portugal	solution, that is cost effective, robust and performant. Specially because use cases can be tailor made for the health care sector, and not a generic solution as most security providers make available on their tools.	point protection engines, anti-virus and anti-malware tools is a must for Sphinx to be able to success in this competitive space.	inside of Sphinx components, this would greatly expand the capabilities of the provided tools, since they could them access potentially a lot more data.	become a center for command and control, not only for security incident but for operational excellence as well, by keeping track of all devices and how they transverse the hospital, great insights could be extracted about usage patterns of the hospital wings and services.	need to get pre authenticated, might it be devices having proper credentials or certificates to access networks, or people to carry RFID crypto cards that identify them and allow or block access to spaces.	approach that could be replicated in multiple hospitals and maintained centrally, using therefor resource more efficiently.	Sphinx so that networks and devices could be naturally sandboxed and have an extra layer of protection against cyberattack.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Traditional hospital insecure networks	IoT technologies and Big Data Real Time Analytics	Nothing is really fully functional yet so that to be able to suggest modifications already	Did not really get the question sorry	Medical services, doctor decision support, patient data processing	Nothing	Did not get the question sorry
EDGENEERING LDA, Portugal	General cybersecurity solutions used by healthcare organisations that were not designed to meet the specific needs of the healthcare IT ecosystem, namely concerning the automated and intelligent features bought by SPHINX that are capable of identifying even unknown threats.	SPHINX could gather cybersecurity-related information provided by third-party malware detection, anti-virus and firewalls software, as well as interoperate with third-party dedicated software to communicate with CERTs.	There is not enough information to answer at this time.	There is not enough information to answer at this time.	SPHINX's intelligent and adaptive features can be applied to other vertical sectors, namely involving transportation, finances and e-government domains.	There is not enough information to answer at this time.	There is not enough information to answer at this time.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Sphinx already incorporates cutting-edge technologies	Sphinx already provides a holistic approach	Nothing	The integrity of the proposed solution shall be destroyed	Every module serves exactly the purpose for which it was initially selected.	Nothing	The selected sequence of things is the most efficient and modifications might hinder the implementation.
Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece	The various security modules	Sphinx can be a bigger solution itself	To have a clear incremental deployment scenario	The solution must be cloud based in order to be able to scale in or out	Other sectors can also benefit	Nothing, I thing an extension is needed	Nothing, I thing an extension is needed
FUNDACION TECNALIA	N/A	N / A	BBTR is actually adapting the	N / A	BBTR in the Project Will be	N / A	N / A

SPHINX Partner	Substitute	Combine	Adopt	Modify	Put to Another Use	Eliminate	Reverse
RESEARCH & INNOVATION , Spain			Blockchain technologies to actually support the Área of auditability.		used for auditability purposes, but it can actually be extended to support data soberaniry.		
5 YGIONOMIKI PERIFERIA THESSALIAS & STEREAS ELLADAS, Greece	Replace and improve the security business process that is currently used in healthcare industry	Yes, it can be part of a bigger solution. It can be attached to current cybersecurity infrastructure so as to result to an advanced Cybersecurity Information System	They way that hospitals collect information, monitor events, assess vulnerable conditions and have decision support capabilities that are almost absent in healthcare organisations	Modify and strengthen the cybersecurity strategy and lead to the adoption of security policies that are almost absent	Monitor hospital assets and perform penetration tests	Instead of doing work manually, SPHINX can integrate many cybersecurity functionalities and improve the results of ICT departments in tangible way.	Through a central monitor dashboard ICT employees will follow a bottom up approach to monitor their assets instead of doing this manually and multiple times
IMPRESA NACIONAL " CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	Malware detection software.	Yes, for instance SPHINX can combine a Security information and event management (SIEM) with vulnerability assessment tools.	SPHINX can be adapted to all cybersecurity proposes.	Modify the SPHINX project making it a more complex solution, might bring higher challenges to test it in healthcare institutions.	SPHINX can be used not only for cybersecurity healthcare systems but also for all business companies that have their production systems based on interconnected digital tools.	SPHINX is a cybersecurity toolkit project, which means that eliminate any component might produce a weaker cybersecurity solution.	Reverse the order of SPHINX components will damage SPHINX architecture which might mean a fail of service.
VILABS (CY) LTD, Cyprus	SPHINX can replace the different cybersecurity solutions that exist in the market.	Not aware of something	-	SPHINX can be a universal tool that can be used by all healthcare units in the world	SPHINX can be used in other domains as well. Not only in the Healthcare sector.	It is early to say that	-
INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS, Greece	Individual cybersecurity related tools could be substituted by an integrated yet modular cybersecurity toolbox	SPHINX appears to be already a combination of tools into a bigger solution	n/a	n/a	n/a	Fragmentation of the cybersecurity armor	n/a
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO DE EVORA EPE, Portugal	SPHINX can replace or complement cybersecurity mechanisms in hospital settings.	Combined with the security mechanisms implemented by IT teams, SPHINX can be an asset. For example, complementing a	SPHINX allows a great capacity to adapt to the most varied security environments, covering the most diverse brands of equipment, such	You must be able, based on artificial intelligence and machine learning, to adapt to any kind of change.	You can be prepared to do the features that allow you to do a thorough search on any new equipment connected to a	At this point it is still premature to remove features without being properly tested.	I don't know.

SPHINX Partner	Substitute	Combine	Adopt	Modify	Put to Another Use	Eliminate	Reverse
		good firewall or good antivirus.	as routers, firewalls, etc.		network, in order to discover harmful software hidden in the machine.		
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	With the introduction of GDPR, privacy has emerged as a very big concern, with the help of SPHINX and in particular the Homomorphic Encryption module, SPHINX will be able to provide hospitals the provision of storing and searching in the encrypted domain thus improving privacy of users and security of the stored data.	SPHINX can be combined with the existing solutions for cloud storage and would enable healthcare professionals to make use of this facility. The HE tool in the SPHINX solution allows healthcare professionals to store information on third party cloud repositories.	Instead of having the HE tool as a backend tool. It can be adapted to have a front end interface, thus allowing users to modify and manage the tool as they deem suitable.	The solution is made with scalability in mind, therefore, the solution should work as expected with increased data size.	The HE tool was initially intended to be used on .txt document. It can be modified to work on more file formats.	The optimisation study is currently being looked into. The codebase and the module would be improved to reduce computational overhead.	The HE tool has been divided into two components to add more value. One deals with network traffic anonymization and the other deals with encryption and search for files that are being uploaded by the healthcare entities.
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX could substitute traditional/conventional honeypots and cybersecurity knowledge base repositories used-deployed in health organizations.	Combine honeypots with Artificial Intelligence towards learning from cyber-attacks. Combine honeypots with digital forensics for collecting and providing evidence of cyber-attacks. Combine knowledge base repository with external databases of common vulnerabilities and exposures, vulnerability assessment reports, post-incident reports and lessons learned towards providing best practices.	Honeypots can start learning from cyber-attacks. Adapt honeypots to use AI for improving intrusion detection, learning from attacks, and thus extend as much as possible the time needed for an adversary to distinguish the honeypot from a real asset. Adapt HPs to exploit acceleration paradigm for improved power consumption and performance gains. Adapt KB to use multiple and heterogeneous sources of cybersecurity related information in order to generate	Miniaturization of the hardware-based HPs (e.g. embedded-system based HPs)	HP & KB could be used in any type of industry that uses ICT technologies and needs protection against cybersecurity threats.	Eliminate complexity in setup and operational configuration.	Not Applicable

SPHINX Partner	Substitute	Combine	Adopt	Modify	Put to Another Use	Eliminate	Reverse
			and provide cyber-security best practices tailored to the health domain.				
SIVECO ROMANIA SA, Romania	Sphinx could substitute traditional DPI methods used to identify application and protocols behind IP and devices.	SPHINX could combine existing open source Technologies- ie Tshark and webshark to create a better tool to monitor data traffic and to detect anomalies.	Anomaly Detection and Data Traffic Monitoring modules could be used in any kind of industry, not only in health domains.	If the usual data traffic increases suddenly it might block existing protection tools of health networks. The new Data Traffic Monitoring and Anomaly Detection modules will solve this problem.	Anomaly Detection module could be used to stop threats to intrude in SPHINX ecosystem.	We are at a stage in which we can not eliminate features and attributes of DTM, AD or Interactive Dashboards	We will keep a constant communication with our partners to spot any opportunity to add value and to improve our modules or other modules in SPHINX.
KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Ireland	Cyber-security solutions – Security incident and event management solutions – Firewall security systems	SPHINX has already a holistic cyber-security approach, at the moment we cannot foresee the need for further combining SPHINX with another, not already planned to be developed, toolkit/component	SPHINX could be modified to fit the needs of any kind of infrastructure and serve as a holistic cyber-security solution	N/A	Not aware, the DSS component, for example, has to be restructured to fit the needs of another user	Up to this moment the overall development of SPHINX is not at a stage where we could efficiently assess if there is a need for eliminating features and/or attributes	Again, it is still early as we have not reached the point where full functionality can be properly assessed

3.13.1.1.3 Key results

Substitute:

- Existing Cybersecurity solutions (e.g. SIEM)
- Current Cybersecurity business processes in health industry

Combine:

- SPHINX components used in a synergistic/complementary way with third party solutions and vendors
- SPHINX components combined to build holistic Cybersecurity solutions

Adapt:

- Tailor Cybersecurity solutions to health organisations needs
- Acquire information from external repositories

Modify:

- Extend SPHINX's scope to provide a holistic Cybersecurity solution (central command and control) by being able to track, monitor and control each device operating in the health organisation
- Cope with the sudden increases in the workload

Put to another use:

- Application of SPHINX solution to other application domains of similar scale
- Provide penetration testing services

Eliminate:

- Complex configuration and setup
- Fragmentation in the Cybersecurity defence
- Manually and error-prone operations

Reverse:

- Use mature and well proven existing standards and technologies to bring SPHINX closer to the market (but farther from its research objectives)
- Abandon flat networking in favour of total virtualised net topologies

3.13.1.2 Get Customer Insight through the Painstorming method

As a second step in the exploration phase we need to start working to empathize with our target customer, in our case Healthcare organisations. What is it that they want to accomplish through SPHINX, and what are their current key pain points where SPHINX could help? Uncovering their key needs or problems will be essential as we will determine the best path forward on our innovation journey. There are many ways to get insight, from doing desk research to conducting interviews. Within SPHINX we will do desk research and apply the Painstorming method². Painstorming will help us elaborate on our customer's key pain points and problems developing a better understanding of their needs.

The **Painstorming** template of **SPHINX** can be accessed through the following link:

<https://forms.gle/6DJJoLajdgBVSkut6>

3.13.1.2.1 SPHINX Painstorming Consolidated Results

Regarding the **Personas** the consortium has identified the Health sector in general (i.e. IT personnel, doctors, nurses and patients) as the customer that we are innovating for with the majority of the answers focussing on the IT and administrative personnel of the health care organisations. For the **Activities** question the majority of the answers was about the everyday work the IT and administrative personnel performs towards supporting the healthcare services provision (e.g. protect against Cybersecurity attacks, maintain patients data, help doctors and nurses to perform their work); there were also answers focussing on the provision of health services as the primary activity. As far as the **Insights** are concerned, the answers revealed that the IT departments are overburdened with the relevant work, the tasks are not clearly defined or even unnecessarily performed, manual operations instead of automated ones are still in practice and that security practices may not be applied rigorously, for example passwords are stored in plain text or even shared amongst the personnel. Finally, the answers about the **Needs** revealed that the “big” pain is the lack of automation in the day to day procedures regarding Cybersecurity tasks and operations.

3.13.1.2.2 Painstorming Responses

This section highlights the partners' contribution in the respective questionnaire and presents their raw answers that were used for deriving the consolidated and key results discussed in the above and below sections.

² <https://itk.mitre.org/painstorming/>

Figure 6 Partners' contribution in PAINSTORMING Responses

Table 5 Partner's PAINSTORMING Responses

SPHINX Partner	Persona	Activities	Insights	Needs
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	The ultimate beneficiary is the patient. All the risks associated with information security in hospitals directly or indirectly have to do with patient safety, even the ones that aren't apparent at first glance. Any security incident at a hospital may affect individual patients directly, or through a disruption, hinder the hospital's ability to perform its primary function to provide health services to patients. At the same time, the existence of these risks for patients create the more immediate to ensure security of the hospitals' IT infrastructure. The end users will be IT professionals in hospitals.	The main functions are to set up, manage, maintain and secure the IT and network infrastructure, while providing support and training services to hospital workers.	When IT departments are overburdened with work and responsibilities, including administrative work related to internal auditing, creating and maintaining security policies etc, they transfer responsibilities to the end-users, for example, allowing users to be local administrators to the computers they are provided with.	Hospital networks, equipment and computers are complex and diverse. It's very difficult to keep track of everything at the same time and have a truly centrally managed active snapshot of their security status. IT professionals need to be aware of it themselves, even if end-users aren't. This means that an imminent threat should be known to the IT professionals as early as possible, and preferably before it becomes an incident or is reported by an end-user.
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO O MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIALDA, Portugal	Healthcare sector providers of goods and services	They mainly work to save lives :). But we work to make their tools safer and available when needed.	No real insight on this.	It's a pain to manage the number of devices in a large organization, security threats come from everywhere, might it be internal or BYODs. Dealing with this complex heterogeneous environment, requires a scalable and easy to manage solution.

SPHINX Partner	Persona	Activities	Insights	Needs
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Hospital management, IT employees, Health sector, Teh Hospital IT ecosystem	Organise the hospital IT ecosystem for the normal and safe functioning of all connected devices. They maintain the hospital ICT system in order to be able to work normally and they further try to introduce the digitisation concepts.	They unnecessarily have to do a variety of trivial tasks such as cleaning doctor's and employees pc's from viruses and spam as there are no advanced security policies applied by all employees.	Having to repeat same processes again due to the lack of knowledge of the other employees.
EDGENEERING LDA, Portugal	IT operators in healthcare organisations	Set-up, monitor and control the healthcare organisation's IT ecosystem to prevent, detect, identify, protect against, respond to and recover from cybersecurity threats, events, incidents and attacks. They are also responsible for reporting cybersecurity events and attacks to the proper authorities.	Manual lengthy processes to investigate cybersecurity events.	The lack of automated and intelligent tools to exercise cybersecurity across the whole IT ecosystem; the lack of integrated perspective of the cybersecurity status in real time of the whole IT ecosystem; the lack of tools to deal with new, unknown and forecasted cyberthreats.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Organizations in health-care sector that want to enhance their Cyber-security posture.	Provide health-related services	Try to tackle the problem with individual initiatives	Cyber-security, Operational integrity & availability.
Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece	Healthcare	Use cyber security tools	They act a problem occurs	Automation in the daily routine
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain	Target persona: Security Departments/IT departments or persons that must ensure cybersecurity in the hospitals while ensuring the service availability.	They actually ensure that the IT infrastructure as well as IoT devices in place are working 24/7 providing reliable and trusted information. The end is to do business as normal with no impact due to IT technical issues. The business target is the focus.	Currently many cybersecurity solutions just warns when things happen. SPHIX goes beyond and enables taking actions before an attack takes place... Among others BBTR does this by informing all members on the blockchain network of new incoming attacks.	They need pre-attacks semi automatic solutions that ensure that they do not have to analyse all the information but rather have filtered information on which to make quick decisions
5 YGIONOMIKI PERIFERIA THESSALIAS & STEREAS ELLADAS, Greece	Innovating for Healthcare ICT departments and Hospital Cybersecurity policies	Put SPHINX toolkit in action and measure its performance so as to adopt the new cybersecurity methodology that proposes	It has not been clearly communicated the pros of the tools at this phase to the healthcare industry and how this could improve hospitals daily digital operations	To carefully evaluate the added value imposed by SPHINX ecosystem deployment
IMPRESA NACIONAL " CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	We are innovating to help TIC professionals working at healthcare institutions to protect computer systems against cyber attacks.	TIC professionals are responsible to keep all healthcare equipment working properly, which will help all medical professionals to perform the necessary treatment to the patients.	The TIC healthcare professionals need to systematically alert healthcare professionals to all the cybersecurity threats.	The risk of a cybersecurity attack that can trigger a failure of service is one pain of TIC professionals working at healthcare institutions.

SPHINX Partner	Persona	Activities	Insights	Needs
INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS, Greece	IT departments / professionals of business entities that offer services by making use of digitized solutions. While SPHINX addresses the health sector vertical, most of its tools can be used on other verticals too	Management of the IT infrastructure of their institute	n/a	Vulnerability of the IT systems they manage and, subsequently over their availability and proper operation
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO DE EVORA EPE, Portugal	Innovation is specific to the health sector, but it must be prepared to adapt easily to any other sector.	i don't know.	i don't know.	i don't know.
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	The healthcare industry	Manage personal data for patients	They store and share personal health records. These are stored in plaintext into their repositories, thus allowing different entities to analyse these records.	Storing personal data in plaintext form increases the possibility of a privacy violation thus causing huge fines according to the GDPR. A mechanism that would reduce such chances is needed.
FINTECH FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	Health organizations/facilities.	They provide professional health services to citizens/patients; this includes also the financial, administration and data management activities surrounding the health provision services.	To access medical devices and laboratory results the person in charge has to provide the passwords every time. To avoid the of physical presence they share these passwords with their colleagues to allow them to use the devices/get the results instead of them.	Physical presence and time consuming (e.g. type passwords) activities to authorize the use of the devices and services.
SIMAVI- Software Imagination and Vision SRL, Romania	The project is innovating for Health personnel: medical staff of all specialities using a computer and other medical devices: doctors & nurses and also for IT specialists working in medical units in different European countries.	Health personnel could be family doctors, that have a more general array of knowledge or specialists in medicine: radiology, ultrasounds, CT scans and others. Nurses are another category of healthcare staff. IT engineers that takes care of networks within different hospitals are also a target for the project.	Medical Staff might not have enough time to pay attention to malicious mails or to perform security procedures, like keeping their passwords confidential and secured.	All the needs that medical staff has are well captured and presented in the enquiries performed under WP7.
KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Ireland	Healthcare infrastructure (clinics, hospitals etc)	Healthcare provision Keep track of patients and their medical files	N/A	Secure and safe network for operational and management processes Ensure patient sensitive data integrity and safety

3.13.1.2.3 Key results

Persona:

- Health sector in general
 - IT and administrative personnel

- Doctors
- Nurses
- Patients

Activities:

- everyday work of the IT and administrative persons on supporting the healthcare services provision
- protect against Cybersecurity attacks
- maintain patients' data
- help doctors and nurses to perform their work

Insights:

- IT departments are overburdened with the relevant work
- the tasks are not clearly defined or even unnecessarily performed
- manual operations instead of automated ones are still in practice
- security practices may not be applied rigorously, for example passwords are stored in plain text or even shared amongst the personnel

Needs:

- Automation in the day to day procedures regarding Cybersecurity tasks and operations.

3.13.1.3 Conclusions of the Exploration phase

During the exploration phase the SCAMPER and Painstorming methods were utilized by providing to the partners two online questionnaires (one for each method). The collected responses indicated that the SPHINX innovations have the potential not only to substitute current cyber security products or services but also to be combined with existing ones towards realising synergistic cyber security solutions tailored to the health application domain. Moreover, the exploration phase revealed that the main need of the end users is the Automation in the day-to-day procedures regarding Cybersecurity tasks and operations.

3.13.2 Definition & Characterisation phase

Once we have a sense of the issues, problems, and needs of the target “customer”, of SPHINX it becomes possible to further define our ideas. The first step would be to look at the specific gaps in knowledge, technology, or resources that exist, and any other business risks. When doing something new, there are always risks. That’s why “risk taking” and overcoming fear of “failure” is so important for innovation. The SPHINX consortium has a very strong focus on innovation, therefore it must provide itself with the right means to assess the maturity of innovations developed within the project and to gain guidance during the project on the most appropriate steps to increase the innovation potential and the innovator’s capacity.

3.13.2.1 SPHINX Key Knowledge Gaps

One way to increase the chances of success from the beginning involves identifying the biggest gaps and risks that exist and coming up with a plan to address these. The Key Knowledge Gaps method will help us identify and list the biggest gaps and risks related to the technologies and approaches suggested within SPHINX. Where possible, identify ways to bridge gaps and mitigate risks. The template can be accessed through the following link: <https://forms.gle/FWMAePTEwbcYqCLh7>

3.13.2.2 SPHINX Key Knowledge Gaps consolidated results

From the collected answers it can be deduced that the technological gaps can be attributed to a) the lack of experience with the relevant technology (especially for products starting at TRL1 level); b) existing technologies immaturity; c) scarce information in the literature about the needed or envisaged technologies and algorithms; d) lack of common technological frameworks and practices tailored to the health sector domain; and e) high heterogeneity amongst the various data sources, including both internal (e.g. SPHINX modules) and external ones (e.g. external threat intelligence repositories). The impacts from the identified gaps were estimated as high when referring to the immaturity or non-existence of the relevant technologies and medium to low when referring to the heterogeneity of the technologies and data sources. As remedies to the mentioned gaps the most predominant ones are the extended literature review, the hire of experts, the use of well-established and well-formed AI technologies/frameworks (e.g. Keras), APIs, and ontologies; and the adoption and adaptation to the SPHINX needs of a common framework that will support the progressive and continuous integration and testing of the developed artefacts. As far as it concerns the nature of the innovation, the majority of them fall either in the Technological either or in the Technological & Scientific Innovation category (see Figure 7).

Nature of the Innovation

23 responses

Figure 7: Nature of the Innovation

3.13.2.3 TRL stats

As far as it concerns the innovations' current TRL status, the majority of them fall between TRL1 and TRL4, depicting as such the RIA nature of the project, whereas the target level of the innovation at the project's end falls mainly between TRL4 and TRL7.

Current State (TRL)
25 responses

Figure 8: Current State (TRL) of the key innovation of SPHINX (M1-M18)

Future State (TRL)
25 responses

Figure 9: Future State (TRL) of the key innovation of SPHINX (M18-M36)

Towards giving some context to the reader, a one to one mapping between the partners’ innovation and the source/destination TRL levels is given in the following table.

Table 6 TRL target per innovation per partner

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIALDA, Portugal	SIEM	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	TRL 9: Actual system proven in operational environment
EDGENEERING LDA, Portugal	Third-Party API	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Network behaviour and attack simulators	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	RISK Assessment	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Forensic Data Collection Engine	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept
Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece	VaaS and Cybersecurity toolkit	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO DE EVORA EPE, Portugal	eCare	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	Homomorphic Encryption	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Artificial Intelligence Honeypots	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Knowledge Base Repository	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab
SIMAVI- Software Imagination and Vision SRL, Romania	Anomaly Detection, Data Traffic Monitoring, Interactive Dashboards	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIALDA, Portugal	SIEM	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain	BlockChain Threat Registry + Auditability Mechanism	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment
IMPRESA NACIONAL " CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	Automated Cybersecurity Certification	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept
KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Ireland	SPHINX DSS and AE	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment
AIDEAS OU, Estonia	Honeypot Intrusion Detection	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	Homomorphic Encryption	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS, Greece	Service Manager	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
IMPRESA NACIONAL CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	Automated Cybersecurity Certification	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept

3.13.2.4 Key Knowledge Gaps Responses

This section highlights the partners’ contribution in the respective questionnaire and presents their raw answers that were used for deriving the consolidated and key results discussed in the above and below sections.

Figure 10 Partners’ contribution in Key Knowledge Gap Responses

Table 7 Partner’s Key Knowledge Gap Responses

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)	Technological Gaps	Impact factor	Remedies
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO O MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIALDA, Portugal	SIEM	Technological Innovation	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	TRL 9: Actual system proven in operational environments	Integration with multiple security appliances from different vendors. Reduced number of out of the box use cases	4	Progressively create integrations with legacy systems, implement ATT&CK mitre framework to increase the number of out-of-the-box threat detections
EDGENEERING LDA, Portugal	Third-Party API	Technological Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Not enough information at this time	2	Not applicable
NATIONAL TECHNICAL	Network behaviour	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL 2: Technology	Lack of effective distributed network emulation tools. Lack of extended	4	

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)	Technological Gaps	Impact factor	Remedies
UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	and attack simulators			concept formulated	bibliography and methodology.		
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	RISK Assessment	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	Complexity, subjectivity, Availability of data	3	
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Forensic Data Collection Engine	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	No common practice. Strongly influenced by the diversity of data and end user's actions.	4	
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Risk assessment and awareness module	Scientific Innovation	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	Connecting disparate data and extracting relevant information from them	3	Using common ontologies
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Attack and behaviour simulator	Technological Innovation	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	Simulating all the different possible events and states	4	Starting by focusing on most important/common ones
Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece	VaaS and Cybersecurity toolkit	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment	Tailored to healthcare domain	4	
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO DE EVORA EPE, Portugal	eCare	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment	Remote setup and installation on end users.	4	
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	Homomorphic Encryption	Technological Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	None	4	
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Artificial Intelligence Honey pots	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	Steep learning curve for AI, adaptation complexities for accelerating ML-based algorithms	4	Literature survey, trial and error, use of proven, widespread used, and well-documented AI frameworks (e.g. Keras, TensorFlow, etc.)
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Knowledge Base Repository	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	Design/develop cyber-security knowledge model tailored in health domain, interfacing with external threat repositories.	4	Literature survey, trial and error, use of external threat repositories using well-formed APIs.

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)	Technological Gaps	Impact factor	Remedies
SIMAVI- Software Imagination and Vision SRL, Romania	Anomaly Detection, Data Traffic Monitoring, Interactive Dashboards	Technological Innovation	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment	One of the difficulties that we are facing now is the big volume of data that our modules are processing.	3	This difficulty will be significant for the System administrators within the hospitals. The impact will be the increase of data processing time. One remedy that we can think of is to delete periodically the data previously processed.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	ABS	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	Discovery of a common virtualisation framework for the automated emulation of network topologies and cyberattack vectors.	3	Extended research and adaptation to the needs and development of the SPHINX platform as a whole.
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIA DA, Portugal	SIEM	Technological Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment	Access to relevant data sources, and massive deployment & management of log source collectors	3	Use our company internal systems, laptops, desktops and servers as guinea pigs
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain	BlockChain Threat Registry + Auditability Mechanism	Technological Innovation	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	There are no Technological gaps, but the difficulties are more linked to the undreadiness of the organisations in cybersecurity, so they are more focused in preventing mechanisms and automating the auditability is considered currently as a less priority...	3	Basically, it consists on making the user aware that have a blockchain threat registry will not only ensure a full real-time guard but that it also allows for the automatic auditability of the system in case of legal responsibilities to third parties as well as ensuring compliance legal regulations.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment	Scientific Innovation	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	At the current stage the designed concept is being tested.	3	

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)	Technological Gaps	Impact factor	Remedies
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Forensic Data Collection Engine	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 1: Basic principles observed	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	The module is currently at the design process. At this stage, the extensive use of diverse data and their management seems to affect heavily the design of the module.	3	
IMPRENSA NACIONAL " CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	Automated Cybersecurity Certification		TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	More interoperability tests are necessary	2	
EDGENEERING LDA, Portugal	SPHINX Third Party API	Technological Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Capability to generalise the API approach able to cope with multiple components, developed by different partners	3	We recruited an expert on Web Services and API responsible to define and implement a robust architecture for the API. The API is designed to support third-party registration and dynamic provision of services in a generalised way
KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Ireland	SPHINX DSS and AE	Technological & Scientific Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	Complexity, Subjectivity, Availability of data as well as extracting relevant information from them, as the module interacts with multiple modules from other partners.	4	Extended research and literature review to match the needs of the SPHINX platform as a whole. Trial and error towards the decision of the most suitable AI framework to work within (e.g. Keras).
AIDEAS OU, Estonia	HoneyPot Intrusion Detection	Scientific Innovation	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated	TRL 5: Technology validated in relevant environment	Training the intrusion detection models on more data	4	?
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	Homomorphic Encryption	Technological Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	The heavy computational requirement of the tool was handled was a risk that was foreseen well in time. We resorted to careful optimisation	3	

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Current State (TRL)	Future State (TRL)	Technological Gaps	Impact factor	Remedies
					of the tool to reduce computational cost with minimum compromise in performance.		
INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS, Greece	Service Manager	Technological Innovation	TRL 4: Technology validated in lab	TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Being part of a middleware, the Service Manager is not meaningful unless properly integrated with / leveraged by other software components. Although not being a technological gap, Integration is always a challenge.	4	Case-by-case analysis
IMPRENSA NACIONAL " CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	Automated Cybersecurity Certification	TRL 2: Technology concept formulated		TRL3: Experimental proof of concept	More interoperability tests are necessary.	2	

3.13.2.5 Key results

Gaps:

- scarce information in the literature about the relevant technologies
- existing technologies immaturity or non-existence of relevant technologies
- lack of experience with the relevant technologies
- lack of common technological frameworks and practices tailored to the health sector domain
- high heterogeneity amongst the various data sources, including both internal and external ones

Impacts:

- high when referring to the immaturity or non-existence of the relevant technologies
- Medium to low when referring to the heterogeneity of the technologies and data sources

Remedies:

- extended literature review
- hiring of experts
- use of well-established and well-formed AI technologies/frameworks (e.g. Keras), APIs, and ontologies
- adoption and adaptation to the SPHINX needs of a common framework that will support the progressive and continuous integration and testing of the developed artefacts

3.13.2.6 Conclusions of the Definition and Characterisation phase

During the Definition and the Characterisation phase the Key knowledge Gaps method was utilised by providing to the partners one online questionnaire. The collected responses revealed the gaps in terms of

knowledge and expertise, and the impact that these gaps may have in the implementation of the SPHINX innovations. To alleviate the identified impacts and assure the proper realisation of the innovations, several mitigation actions (remedies) were identified focusing mainly in acquiring the missing expertise via the literature survey and/or via hiring the appropriate experts and on the other hand by promoting common frameworks for addressing interoperability issues.

3.13.3 Building a business case

3.13.3.1 SWOT Analysis

Innovations should not be pursued without a solid business case in place for why that innovation is necessary. Unless there is a plan in place to ensure the innovation will support future business growth, it will likely not lead to sustainable growth. As a first step towards this direction is the implementation of a SWOT analysis report. SWOT Analysis is a strategic thinking method that helps reveal the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to an idea or business strategy. Please access the template through the following link:

<https://forms.gle/Kf13QErYgEtXbTCb7>

3.13.3.1.1 SPHINX SWOT Analysis consolidated results

The collected answers, while tangled to the specific tool that each partner develops, share some common characteristics. For the Strengths these are the use of AI to automate/facilitate tasks and increase performance, the enhanced interoperability with third party tools, the improved usability and the tailoring to the needs of the hosting healthcare organisation. On the other hand, the Weaknesses answers reveal increased maintenance and developing costs, that the integration of SPHINX in one solution consists on integrating different tools with distinct IPR, and that an extensive simulation of real systems will increase the solution's complexity. As far as it concerns the opportunities, the answers highlight the existence of high-volume markets, the use of open source platforms, and the applicability of the solution to different market and application domains. Finally for the Threats, the common pattern that emerges shows interoperability/integration failures both amongst SPHINX components and also with the third party solutions; advancements in competitive, especially open source, solutions; and loose of the communities that support the tools that SPHINX builds upon.

3.13.3.1.2 SWOT Analysis Responses

This section highlights the partners' contribution in the respective questionnaire and presents their raw answers that were used for deriving the consolidated and key results discussed in the above and below sections.

Figure 11 Partners' contribution in SWOT Responses

Table 8 Partners' SWOT Responses

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	STRENGTHS	Weaknesses	Opportunities	THREATS
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIALDA, Portugal	Metadon SIEM	Technological Innovation	Price, Fast Performance, Ease of Maintenance, Ease of onboarding new sources, Extensibility	Maturity, Not feature Heavy, Brand Awareness	High volume markets, where the scale of information is huge, and where commercial sources are expensive, or open-source solutions are not easy to deploy and maintain	Advancements in opensource solutions that make the product lose its competitive edge on the performance and usability fronts
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Network behaviour and attack simulators	Technological & Scientific Innovation	New scientific fields, freedom of choice of tools and methodologies.	Lack of relative literature and similar applications. Relatively old and weak toolbox.	Possibly new fields of research	Difficulty of integration with the rest of components
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Risk Assessment	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Prompt quantitative notification, aggregate impact on operational	Quantitative approach needs interpretation of knowledge into numeric values.	A concrete outcome can be further analysed and applied to other sectors.	Failure to assemble the required information.

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	STRENGTHS	Weaknesses	Opportunities	THREATS
			and/or physical level.			
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Forensic Data Collection Engine	Technological & Scientific Innovation	New procedure to provide evidence in the aftermath of a cyber-incident.	User's input is crucial. Timely availability of data.	The use of advanced modules in SPHINX can provide the appropriate information.	Scarce and difficult to be correlated data. User's consistency.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Risk Analysis and Awareness Module	Scientific Innovation	Ability to get real time analysis about the state of your network, leading to actionable data that can be used in decision making.	Need for initial user input and large dataset to gauge effectiveness	Can be added in existing system monitoring systems	Over reliance on analysis, rather than the problem at hand
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Attack and Behaviour Simulator	Technological Innovation	Gives the ability to test a system reliant on network traffic in "almost real" environment	Difficult to simulate all possibilities due to how networks operate.	Can be used by tools before being deployed in real environments	Attacks and incidents not covered by the tool, won't have been tested and may still pose issues even after using the tool.
Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece	VAaaS & cyber toolkit	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Tailored to Healthcare	Based on Open source tool	enhance the open source community tool	Loose the community supporting the tools
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain	BBTR - Blockchain Based threat Registry	Technological Innovation	It provides a reliable manner to ensure that if a node in the network is attacked all the other nodes in the networks are aware that a new attack is coming, and they can act before it happens in their Enterprise.	It is tightly dependent in a SIEM and attack detection tools, which within SPHINX Project we are dependent on other partners.	The proposed solution ensures a inviolable solution that can inform all organisation sharing a blockchain based network when one of the nodes is attacked as well as providing the available details on the potential solutions to the attacks. Current main approach to this is the MISP ecosystem but is still using methods that can be attacked by hackers while our solution being implemented over blockchain and the attackers cannot succeed in bridging into the network.	The main thread is so to what extend the actual perception of thread by the potential users. This is an extra cost is inferred for the BBTR deployment that may not see as necessary if looking at the costs.
VILABS (CY) LTD, Cyprus	SPHINX integrated platform (notice that we are not the main IPR holder but we	Technological Innovation	Many components covering everything a customer would	Different partners hold the IPRs, Solution depends on integration of different	Health care market is big and is growing, Increased concern for cybersecurity	Competition, Lack of interoperability in medical equipment

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	STRENGTHS	Weaknesses	Opportunities	THREATS
	are willing to work on the business potential of the integrated solution)		require, Effortless operation	technologies not widely accepted in the market		
IMPRESA NACIONAL “ CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	SPHINX Sandbox	Technological Innovation	SPHINX sandbox allows to replicate the healthcare software system without interfere with the normal performance of the healthcare institutions.	SPHINX sandbox will be replicate a real environment.	SPHINX sandbox brings the opportunity to test a real system.	The main threat of the sandbox is the software compatibility.
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO DE EVORA EPE, Portugal	eCare	Technological Innovation	Remote monitoring of patients and environments safely, with interaction with doctors in hospitals.	At this stage, it is still premature to know the weaknesses.	The opportunities are immense: patients can be monitored in the comfort of their homes, medications can be changed based on this medication, an emergency means can be activated based on vital parameters, etc.	Alteration of data, theft of clinical information, man in the middle, etc.
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	Homomorphic Encryption	Technological Innovation	It allows users to search in the encrypted domain. It also allows healthcare professionals involved in different organisations to perform a double sided blinded search.	It is computationally expensive.	This tool can be used by multiple entities who intend to search for information in each other's database without having to reveal their information.	None identified as of now.
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Artificial Intelligence Honeypots	Technological & Scientific Innovation	AI, accelerated, multiple flavors (i.e. physical and virtual HPs)	Increased cost for developing, testing and validating accelerated algorithms.	Open-source AI frameworks and algorithms, Increased need for cyber-security protection.	Numerous commercial HP solutions are already available.
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Knowledge Base Repository	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Extract knowledge from multiple sources, cyber-security knowledge model tailored to health domain	Increased cost for maintaining and updating the knowledge model to reflect the continuous changes in the cyber-threat landscape.	Increased need for cyber-security awareness, training, and best-practices.	Use third parties™ information source (e.g. use of external threat repositories)

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	STRENGTHS	Weaknesses	Opportunities	THREATS
SIMAVI- Software Imagination and Vision SRL, Romania	Anomaly Detection, Data Traffic Monitoring, Interactive Dashboards	Technological Innovation	DTM- allows creation and use of many interfaces in parallel in the same time; DTM will manage Tshark on more than one device in parallel AD- algorithms for anomaly detection will be created and used ID- displays graphical information for more components in the same time	DTM- large volume of data to be processed AD- large volume of data to be processed, increase in response time ID “ is subject to users opinion “ might not be considered user friendly	AD, DTM and ID: each of them represents an opportunity to research and create a tool that will better fit the end users needs of protection against Cyber attacks	One possible threat will be the malfunction of the system, if blocked by a huge volume of data. Other possible threat is that the user of these modules needs to be highly digitally skilled.
KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Ireland	Decision Support System [DSS]	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Decision Support on operational and risk management Provide insights prior to an event (attack) and propose mitigation actions Machine learning	The outcome relies on the data available Up to this moment, not able to predict all types of attack	Healthcare industry need for a holistic cybersecurity solution with the ability to enhance situational awareness, predict possible threats and propose mitigation actions	Regulation changes (although SPHINX and all its components are being developed according to the latest regulations)

3.13.3.1.3 Key results

Strengths:

- AI to automate/facilitate tasks and increase performance,
- the enhanced interoperability with third party tools,
- the improved usability
- the tailoring to the needs of the hosting healthcare organisation

Weakness:

- increased maintenance and developing costs,
- integration of SPHINX in one solution consists on integrating different tools with distinct IPR
- extensive simulation of real systems will increase the solution’s complexity

Opportunities:

- high-volume markets,
- use of open source platforms,
- applicability of the solution to different market and application domains

Threats:

- interoperability/integration failures both amongst SPHINX components and also with the third-party solutions
- advancements in competitive, especially open source solutions
- losing the communities that support the tools that SPHINX builds upon

3.13.3.2 Innovation Horizons Model

Part of the process of aligning expectations comes through horizon planning. The Innovation Horizons Model, also called the three horizons model, is a framework that organizations can use to identify areas for innovation and improvement without losing sight of current performance. The Innovation Horizons Model will be used to outline the different innovation priorities of SPHINX over time, the products and services to be explored within each of those horizons, and the details related to business model and strategic approach to each horizon. The innovation horizons template can be accessed through the following link:

<https://forms.gle/jQDKzPkBBMpeo5k2A>

3.13.3.2.1 SPHINX Innovation Horizons Model consolidated results

For each horizon time, the questionnaires were eliciting answers for the scope, the strategic focus, the competitors and the markets of each SPHINX partner in relevance with their associated solutions and tools.

For Horizon 1 (M1-M18 of the project), the scope of most of the partners was to design their solution and tools, to gain insight about the used technologies and to implement some basic proof of concept use cases; in the same wavelength, the strategic focus (evidently influenced from the scope's answers) was aiming to the solutions design, implementation, interoperability and testing; one partner clearly stated that focuses to monetise their solution when SPHINX hits the healthcare market. For the competitors, the answers indicated that each partner was identifying as competition another product/company providing similar Cybersecurity services. For the markets, the answers revealed that the majority of the partners aim to the healthcare sector while a few answers showed the interest for other domains like education, Cybersecurity and also the focus on specific geographical locations like the Romanian and EU markets.

For Horizon 2 (M19-M36 of the project), the scope of most of the partners is to finalise, test and validate their solution and tools; in the same direction, the strategic focus is aiming to improve user experience, enhance the accuracy and efficiency of the SPHINX tools and validate them on the pilot testbeds; furthermore one partner stated that their focus is to integrate some of the SPHINX components with their company's own solutions. For the competitors, the answers were similar to Horizon 1 answers indicating that each partner was identifying as a competitor companies or products providing similar Cybersecurity services. For the markets, the same pattern as the in Horizon 1 was observed with the partners aiming primarily to the healthcare sector and to the Cybersecurity solution providers market, including digital identity management.

Finally for Horizon 3 (2 years period after the project's end), the scope of most of the partners is to further enhance their solutions, provide maintenance and test their solutions on real production environments; following the same approach, the strategic focus is aiming to further improve the delivered user experience, validate the SPHINX tools on the pilot market and increase the further the TRL achieved from the project. For the competitors, the answers were similar to Horizon 1 and 2 answers indicating that each partner was identifying as a competitor companies or products providing similar Cybersecurity services. As far as it concerns the markets, the same pattern as in Horizon 1 and 2 were observed with the partners aiming primarily to the

healthcare sector and to the Cybersecurity solution providers market, including the certification and cyber range sectors.

3.13.3.2.2 Innovation Horizons Responses

This section highlights the partners’ contribution in the respective questionnaire and presents their raw answers that were used for deriving the consolidated and key results discussed in the above and below sections.

Figure 12 Partners’ contribution in Horizons model Responses

Table 9 Partners' Horizons model Responses

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets
PDM E FC PROJECTO DESENVOLVIMENTO MANUTENCAO FORMACAO E CONSULTADORIA, Portugal	Metadon SIEM	Technological Innovation	Manage security events from all sources and device types	Holistic security events management	ELK, Splunk, Alien Vault	Security Information and Event Management	Manage security events from all sources and device types	User Experience, User Extensibility, Threat Detection	FireEye, QRadar, ArcSight	Log & Event Management	SIEM & Threat Detection	Deliver upstanding user experience	AlienVault Fireeye ArcSight QRadar LogRhythm Splunk	Log & Event Management
EDGENEERING LDA, Portugal	Third-party API	Technological Innovation	The SPHINX Third-party API provides a programmatic interface with the SPHINX solution. In this context, it enables third-parties to either develop additional components atop the SPHINX solution or to integrate specific SPHINX components in their own solutions. In addition, the SPHINX Third-party API is useful for certification authorities to	EDGE will monetise the SPHINX Third-party API by joining the SPHINX partners as they offer the SPHINX System and Tools to the healthcare market.	Companies providing general cybersecurity solutions that lack a third-party API.	Healthcare market	The SPHINX Third-party API provides a programmatic interface with the SPHINX solution. In this context, it enables third-parties to either develop additional components atop the SPHINX solution or to integrate specific SPHINX components in their own solutions. In addition, the SPHINX Third-party API is useful for	Aside from monetising the SPHINX Third-party API by joining the SPHINX partners as they offer the SPHINX System and Tools to the healthcare market, EDGE will explore the SPHINX Third-party API to integrate specific components of the SPHINX solution within the company's solutions and to test the	Companies providing general cybersecurity solutions that lack a third-party API. Companies providing patient monitoring solutions that lack sound cybersecurity features, cybersecurity certification seal and a third-party API.	Healthcare market	The SPHINX Third-party API provides a programmatic interface with the SPHINX solution. In this context, it enables third-parties to either develop additional components atop the SPHINX solution or to integrate specific SPHINX components in their own solutions. In addition, the SPHINX Third-	Aside from monetising the SPHINX Third-party API by joining the SPHINX partners as they offer the SPHINX System and Tools to the healthcare market, EDGE will explore the SPHINX Third-party API to integrate specific components of the SPHINX solution within the company's solutions and to test the	Companies providing general cybersecurity solutions that lack a third-party API. Companies providing assisted living and smart care solutions that lack sound cybersecurity features, cybersecurity certification seal and a third-party API.	Healthcare , Assisted Living and Public Safety markets

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets
			receive detailed information on the cybersecurity conformity of devices, components, systems or applications.				certification authorities to receive detailed information on the cybersecurity conformity of devices, components, systems or applications.	cybersecurity conformance level of the company's solutions. The cybersecurity features and the certification seal provided by SPHINX are a competitive advantage to the company's solutions portfolio.			party API is useful for certification authorities to receive detailed information on the cybersecurity conformity of devices, components, systems or applications.	cybersecurity conformance level of the company's solutions. The cybersecurity features and the certification seal provided by SPHINX are a competitive advantage to the company's solutions portfolio.		
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Network Behaviour and Attack Simulators	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Emulate representative network traffic	Create a pilot-similar network behaviour background	Network simulators, Traffic classification services	Cybersecurity	Network behaviour and attacks injection	Broaden capabilities and scalability of the emulated network	Network simulators	Cybersecurity and attack simulation	Research on attack emulations in realistic conditions for system testing	Fully function and user-friendly interface integrating all system capabilities	Honeytraps	Cybersecurity, Education, System Testing
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	RISK ASSESSMENT MODULE	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Design Risk assessment model	Design a new approach to assess and analyse risks in the field of cybersecurity	None	Risk Management solutions	Implement, test and validate the model	Publications & further exploitation of knowledge	None	Risk Management Solutions	Fine-tune the risk model and expand its applicability to other fields	Strong background and high quality research work in the specific field, promoting scientific excellence	None	Risk Management
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Risk assessment and awareness module	Scientific Innovation	Create baseline risk assessment and awareness	-	-	-	Fine tune results and ensure changes in data are accurately	Precision of results	-	-	Expanding events that are taken into account - Interoperability with other systems	Expansion of capabilities	Similar tools	System awareness

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets
ATHENS, Greece							reflected in the system							
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Attack and behaviour simulator	Technological Innovation	Establishing basic simulation scenarios	-	-	-	Expanding simulation events	-	-	-	Ensuring validity and similarity to real life scenarios	-	-	-
Hellenic Mediterranean University, Greece	VAAA and Cyber security toolkit	Technological & Scientific Innovation	enhance academic procedure	Academia	No competitors	Education	The scope is to enhance our students competence	Our focus is to enhance our students competence	No competitors	Does not apply to academia	Enhance and prepare our students to future needs	Enhance and prepare our students to future needs	no competitors	Education is free of charge
FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain	BBTR and auditing mechanisms	Technological Innovation	The provision of an BBTR and auditing mechanisms to enable the action against attacks before they occur.	In TECNALIA we are having an initial strategic decision of creating a potential start-up that will take over all Blockchain solutions done so far. In this direction BBTR and the auditing mechanisms are under	It is still early to answer since a company offering blockchain as such is not competitive against already blockchain companies offering solutions for vertical markets, we are considering aligning it with data related innovations.	Once again still under strategic thinking but potentially focusing in all markets in which data usage and analytics is key for their business.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets
				consideration.										
VILABS (CY) LTD, Cyprus	SPHINX Integrated solution	Technological Innovation	Design and development	Develop innovative solution	Will be available at a later stage in the exploitation plan	Will be available at a later stage in the exploitation plan	Development, deployment and partial validation	Evaluation from the pilots	-	-	Explore the possibility to make business out of SPHINX	Identify business opportunities	-	-
IMPRESA NACIONAL “CASA DA MOEDA, S. A., Portugal	Digital security	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Gain knowledge into cybersecurity risk assessment.	Focus on the architecture and development of cybersecurity risk assessment tools.	All companies with digital security solutions	Digital healthcare, digital identification	Cybersecurity certification components	Gain knowledge into cybersecurity certification components	Digital cybersecurity business companies.	Digital healthcare, digital identification.	Cybersecurity certification	Focus on business companies that have a need to certify their digital communications.	Cybersecurity certification business companies	Cybersecurity certification market
HOSPITAL DO ESPIRITO SANTO DE EVORA EPE, Portugal	Ecare	Technological & Scientific Innovation	remote and secure monitoring of patients in their homes.	Implement and use the system in the interaction between patients and the hospital.	Edge, HESE	Healthcare sector	Test the solution in a controlled environment on virtual patients.	Implement and use the system in the interaction between patients and the hospital.	Edge and HESE.	Health sector.	Place the solution in a production environment with guaranteed information security.	Use HESE as the primary user and readjust the solution when necessary.	Edge and HESE.	Health Market.
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	AI HP		a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a	a
TECH INSPIRE LTD, United Kingdom	Homomorphic Encryption	Technological Innovation	The scope of the innovation is to provide a double sided blinded search tool to organisations	The focus is to have improved performance with reduced computation	Cyborg	Healthcare organisations	Refine and optimisation of the solution	Simplifying the solution	Cyborg	Healthcare organisations	Market the whole SPHINX solution with the HE tool embedded into it.	Explore organizations that heavily rely on third party cloud resources and/or	Cyborg	Healthcare

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets
			that intend to share information in a privacy compliant manner.	onal complexity , thus making the proposed solution a preferred choice.								heavily depend upon sharing personal information over insecure medium		
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Artificial Intelligence Honeyports	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Cyber security - Deception of cyber attackers	Asses existing HP solutions - Design HP prototype	Honeyport solution providers	Health organizations/facilities	Cyber security - Deception of cyber attackers	Improve HP with AI and safe layer concepts to gain advantage over existing solutions	HP solution providers	Health organizations/facilities	Cyber security - Deception of cyber attackers	Validate HP solution to the market , Raise TRL from 6 to 7 or 8.	HP solution providers	Health organizations/facilities , SMEs
FINT FUTURE INTELLIGENCE LIMITED, Cyprus	SPHINX Knowledge Base Repository	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Cyber security - Awareness, training, knowledge	Design KB prototype	Cybersecurity Knowledge Base solution providers	Health organizations/facilities	Cyber security - Awareness, training, knowledge	Improve KB to generate/provide cybersecurity best practices tailored to the needs of the deploying organization by leveraging different data sources towards gaining advantage over existing solutions	Cybersecurity Knowledge Base solution providers	Health organizations/facilities	Cyber security - Awareness, training, knowledge	Validate KB solution to the market , Raise TRL from 6 to 7 or 8, Integrate KB to Cyber-range platforms.	Cybersecurity Knowledge Base solution providers	Health organizations/facilities , SMEs, Cyber range solution providers
SIMAVI-Software Imagination and Vision SRL, Romania	Anomaly Detection; Data Traffic Monitoring; Interactive	Technological Innovation	During the first 18 months of SPHINX project,our scope was to build and develop AD, DTM and ID modules in a	Our strategic focus was to align AD, DTM and ID modules with the requireme	N/a	We have in mind Romania and European markets.	For the next period: M19-M36, our scope will be to further develop AD, DTM and ID modules in order to reach	Our strategic focus will be that our modules will work in production and test environments .	N/a.	Romanian and European Markets	Our scope on long term is to ensure that our modules will continue functioning.	As a business strategy focus, this will be to find other medical units in Romania that could be interested in	N/a	Romanian and European markets

SPHINX Partner (Main IPR holder)	Innovation Title	Nature of the Innovation	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets	Scope	Strategic focus	Competitors	Markets
	Dashboards		TRL 3 stage – Experimental proof of concept.	nts from D2.6 - Sphinx Architecture.			TR7 level - System prototype demonstration in operational environment. This cannot be done without building all necessary connections with other components of SPHINX framework.					using SPHINX framework, or at least our modules.		
KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Ireland	Decision Support System [DSS]	Technological & Scientific Innovation	Predict if an attack will occur in the system	Enhance situational awareness – Provide decision support	Toolkits with similar functionalities and other event management tools	Currently, the Healthcare are industry (DSS has to be configured according to the needs of each market)	Enhance the ability to predict an attack prior to its occurrence Propose mitigation actions upon the occurrence of an attack Provide analytics for the attacks (e.g. frequency of occurrence of each attack type)	Enhance situational awareness – Provide decision support	Toolkits with similar functionalities and other event management tools	Currently, the Healthcare are industry (DSS has to be configured according to the needs of each market)	Increase accuracy – Provide analytics that show the efficiency of the suggestions and the actions taken upon an attack	Expand the functionality of DSS	Toolkits with similar functionalities and other event management tools	Explore new markets beyond Healthcare industry
AIDEAS OU, Estonia	Honeypot Intrusion Detection	Scientific Innovation	Novel ML/AI models	Cybersecurity and healthcare	Many	Many	Novel ML/AI models	Cybersecurity and healthcare	Many	Many	Novel ML/AI models	Cybersecurity and healthcare	Many	Many

3.13.3.2.3 Key results

Horizon 1 (M1-M18)

Scope:

- design their solution and tools
- to gain insight about the used technologies
- to implement some basic proof of concept use cases

Strategic Focus:

- solutions design, implementation, interoperability and testing
- monetise their solution when SPHINX hits the healthcare market.

Competitors:

- products/companies providing similar Cybersecurity services

Markets:

- Domains:
 - healthcare sector
 - education
 - Cybersecurity
- Geographical locations
 - Local (Romanian) and EU markets.

Horizon 2 (M19-M36)

Scope:

- finalise, test and validate their solution and tools to gain insight about the used technologies

Strategic Focus:

- improve user experience
- enhance the accuracy and efficiency of the SPHINX tools and validate them on the pilot testbeds
- integrate some of the SPHINX components with their company's own solutions

Competitors:

- products/companies providing similar Cybersecurity services

Markets:

- Domains:
 - healthcare sector
 - education
 - Cybersecurity solutions
 - digital identity management
- Geographical locations

- Local (Romanian) and EU markets.

Horizon 3 (2 years post project period)

Scope:

- enhance developed solutions
- provide maintenance
- test solutions on real production environments

Strategic Focus:

- improve the delivered user experience
- validate the SPHINX tools on the market and increase further the TRL achieved from the project

Competitors:

- products/companies providing similar Cybersecurity services

Markets:

- Domains:
 - healthcare sector
 - education
 - Cybersecurity
 - Certification
- Geographical locations
 - Local (Romanian) and EU markets.

3.13.3.3 Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas was originally introduced by Alexander Osterwalder in his book Business Model Generation, and was based on his earlier work on Business Model Ontology. The Business Model Canvas is a design template that lays out nine building blocks for any business, whether a for-profit company or nonprofit organization. The different dimensions of business model design include:

1. **Customer segments:** The different types of customers that a company targets to build a successful business model
2. **Customer relationships:** The kind of relationships the company wants to have with its customer in order to be successful
3. **Value propositions:** The things that distinguish a company from its competitors in order to better meet the needs of its customers
4. **Key activities:** The most important activities directly related to reinforcing a company's value proposition
5. **Key partners:** The buyer-supplier relationships to create competitive advantage and reduce risk
6. **Key resources:** The most important resources needed to create customer value

7. **Channels:** Effective channels are important to distribute a company's value proposition in ways that are fast, efficient and cost effective. This can be done through its own channels (store front), partner channels (distributors), or a combination
8. **Cost structure:** The most important monetary consequences while operating under different business models
9. **Revenue streams:** The way a company makes money from each customer segment.

The business canvas of SPHINX can be accessed from the following link:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KpF1b_RuzHWA6YIR3S4sumNYLr0piSE6/view?usp=sharing

3.13.3.1 SPHINX Business Model Canvas

3.13.3.2 Description of the SPHINX Business Model Canvas

In this subsection we present a preliminary version of the SPHINX Business Model canvas based on the answers provided by the SPHINX consortium to the various innovation management questionnaires.

Customers served: Starting from the “Customers” for whom we are delivering the value (and would be willing to pay for the SPHINX product), the consortium identified three types of customers: a) Public and private healthcare organisations (hospitals, clinics and care centres), b) Insurance companies and c) Certification authorities. A more detailed analysis of the needs of the SPHINX customers will be presented in “D8.9 Market analysis”.

What is SPHINX offering to its customers (value): Moving to the “Value propositions” segment which is the value that we are delivering to our customers and the needs that we are satisfying, SPHINX provides a) an automated and intelligent Cybersecurity protection mechanism for the healthcare sector (protection against Cybersecurity attacks, maintaining patients’ data, help healthcare workers to perform their work), b) the ability to certify devices, systems, components and applications.

What relationships is SPHINX establishing with its customers (customer relationships): The customer relationships as these are defined by the SPHINX consortium are: a) Long-term, meaning that SPHINX will interact with the customers on a recurring basis, b) Personal assistance meaning that the customer can communicate with SPHINX after a purchase is complete (onsite, through email, call centres etc.), c) training sessions, workshops and pitch events that will be organised for the customers by SPHINX.

What are the resources that underpin this business model: Every business model requires Key Resources to run. In SPHINX the consortium identified: a) IT infrastructure, b) Human resources for research, development and support, c) Human resources for marketing purposes.

Which activities are needed in this business model (key activities): The most important things SPHINX must do to make its business model work are: a) Further development and integration, b) continuous testing and validation, c) marketing and sales.

Which partners leverage this business model: The partnerships and the network that will make the business model work are the following: a) SPHINX consortium (mainly the developers of the components and the business experts willing to take up the results), b) Public and private healthcare organisations (Hospitals, clinics, care centres), c) Insurance companies, d) Medical / healthcare device providers, e) Certification authorities.

Which channels are being used: SPHINX communicates with and reaches the customers to deliver the value proposition with the following ways: a) Online channels (website, social media), b) Sales partners/distributors, c) Healthcare authorities, d) certification authorities.

Which key resources / activities are most expensive (cost structure): The costs that are important to operate the SPHINX business model are the following: a) Development and integration costs, b) Marketing and Sales costs, c) Training costs, d) Infrastructure and cloud service costs.

How would the customers prefer to pay for SPHINX (revenue streams): The revenue streams that represent the way SPHINX will generate cash from the customers are the following: a) Subscription fees, b) Direct sales (one-time payment), c) Licensing fees (scalability), d) Maintenance and support fees, e) Training and consulting fees.

In this section we presented a preliminary version of the SPHINX Business model, using the Business Model Canvas methodology. A more detailed version will be outlined in “D8.7 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v2” on M24 and in “D8.10: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3” on M36.

3.13.3.4 Final updates on the activities related to the development of the SPHINX business model

As part of T8.3 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans and in collaboration with the Innovation management task the SPHINX business model has been developed. The business model considers the further development needed for all the components (to reach the requested TRL 7) and the IPRs related to the acquisition of rights for use of the different components that have been developed by all technical partners.

The SPHINX business model is the result of:

- A thorough examination of the available business models/strategies for similar software solutions.
- Two business modelling workshops that were held with SPHINX consortium (M25 and M34) where all partners had the opportunity to state their views.
- The main results of the SPHINX Toolkit evaluation that is derived from WP7.
- The results of a Market Analysis that is being conducted in “D7.1 Market Analysis”.

The SPHINX business model can be implemented by any legal entity that is willing to utilize the results of the SPHINX project. This legal entity could also be the result of an official collaboration between partners of the SPHINX consortium.

It must be noted that SPHINX is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) project and the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the SPHINX components that constitute the SPHINX Toolkit ranges from 3 to 6 (as also promised in the SPHINX Grant Agreement). That means that in order to reach TRL 7 (system prototype demonstration in operational environment) further development is needed for all the different components involved.

The SPHINX business model is based on the major exploitable outcome of the project is the SPHINX Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for the Health and Care Domain that enhances the cyber protection of the healthcare IT ecosystem and ensures the patients’ data privacy and integrity. The SPHINX Toolkit offers an embedded, smart and robust security awareness layer, able to identify modern and advanced cyber threats, enhanced with a personalised data security management tool.

SPHINX Toolkit has a modular architecture comprising 5 building blocks and 20 key components thus providing the capability to concentrate and handle the data of many devices or services, thus covering a wide range of use case scenarios. The end-users of the SPHINX Toolkit are kept informed at any time via highly comprehensive live dashboards and visual analytics, while being able to interact with the services and functions of the proposed solution in an intuitive and user-friendly way.

3.13.3.5 Conclusions of the Business case phase

During the Business phase a SWOT analysis was performed followed form the compilation of the Business Canvas model. The former together with the results that were derived from the questionnaires of the “Exploration” and “Definition and Characterisation” phases revealed insights to the latter regarding the key strengths and opportunities of the overall SPHINX solution (translated as value proposition, key strengths and activities), the customer segments, the distribution channels and the possible revenue streams. More information about the SPHINX business model can be found in D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plans v3 that will be delivered on Month 39 of the project (March 2022).

3.13.3.6 Innovation Radar Tool questionnaire results

As already mentioned in 3.7.1, the Innovation Radar Tool provides a set of Questions (we used 16 specific questions), listed in Table 3. Based on the assessment questionnaire’s provided answers the innovation Potential and the Innovators Capacity was elicited.

3.13.3.6.1 Questionnaire specific to each SPHINX innovation

The online questionnaire was used for eliciting the answers from the partners was available in this [link](#).

For each question a summary of the answers using plots and text is provided. The Complete questionnaire is provided in section.

The excel file containing the partner’s is uploaded to the project’s online repository (Alfresco) and is available upon request.

To give some context the following table lists the partners that filled the questionnaire and the number of questionnaires they filled in (i.e., one per owning innovation).

No	Partners	Number of questionnaires
1	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	3
2	PDMFC	3
3	FINT	2
4	Software Imagination and Vision - SIMAVI	3
5	TECNALIA	1
6	Intracom Telecom	1
7	KT	1
8	TechInspire	1
9	Hellenic Mediterranean University	1
10	AIDEAS	1
11	EDGENEERING	1

Questions:

1. Is the innovation developed within the project?

As the figure displays, the majority of the innovations is still under development meaning that further time will still be needed until these innovations reach a TRL7 and above level that will allow for their exploitation as a commercial product/service.

2. Characterise the type of innovation

More than half of SPHINX innovations are anticipated to lead to new products in the portfolio of the innovation owning companies; nevertheless, the rest of them are improving an existing product that may also lead to a brand-new product.

3. Characterise the macro type of innovation

Most of the innovations (54%) are expected to lead to a product; standalone or coupled with a service (consulting or non) painting a promising picture for building several business use cases and maximizing revenue streams from a single innovation. It is worth mentioning that 23% of the innovation owners are not yet sure on how to characterise their innovation type, suggesting that either the innovation needs more time to mature and thus reveal its potential application use or that some form of counseling would assist the innovation owners to form a clearer picture on the matter.

4. Will the innovation be introduced to the market or deployed within a partner

Will the innovation be introduced to the market or deployed within a partner?

- Introduced new to the market (commercial exploitation)
- Deployed within a partner (internal exploitation: Changes in organisation, new internal processes implemented, etc.)
- No exploitation planned

Most of the innovations aim to reach the market at some point in the future; nevertheless, there is a significant portion of them (21%) that will be used internally to enable changes in the organization, apply new processes/tools, etc. Finally, several of the innovations will be given as open source and therefore no exploitation activities are planned.

5. If no exploitation is planned, please explain why no exploitation is planned

The service/product will be offered as an opensource application and therefore no exploitation activities are planned.

6. Is there a clear owner of the innovation in the consortium or multiple owners?

All of the relevant answers indicated that there is a clear owner (i.e. the partner leading the development of the innovation)

7. Indicate who is the "owner" of the innovation

The partner leading the development of the innovation (see below table for details).

Name of Organisation	Innovation description
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Facilitation of forensics process by analysing, compiling, combining and correlating incident-related information and data from different levels patterns and contexts in a privacy-aware manner.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Automation framework, partially based on AI, capable of realistically simulating normal user behaviour as well as attack patterns based on real-life data.
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece	Proactive or/and prompt response to cyber events can be enhanced by replacing the offline risk analysis, with an active, online and almost real-time one.
PDMFC	The process and a prototype of the combination of components provide the opportunity to conduct security tests and monitor software services or systems

Name of Organisation	Innovation description
	for compliance and retrieve using host monitoring information regarding vulnerabilities, policy mismatching, and alert for any potential violations.
PDMFC	Anonymize personal data from files or databases. The anonymization works using data minimization and pseudonymization. Working with models of data management and integration with various digital resources (e.g. files, databases).
PDMFC	The SIEM stores, indexes, and aggregates collected logs from multiple resources. By using scheduled queries triggers alerts. The log files can be either constructed data (csv, json) or could be simple text-log files. Extra inputs involve the subscription and publish to KAFKA topics.
FINT	Cyber security Knowledge Base (KB) repository provides shareable and actionable cyber-threat intelligence information for both human and machine cyber-security actuators and plays a key role in collaborative threat analysis, automated threat exchange and automated detection and response.
FINT	Smart virtual and hardware decoys utilising AI, containerisation and acceleration (HW flavour) to maximise learning from the manifested cyber attacks, to prevent tampering of logs, and to accelerate edge based attack analysis, serving as early detection warning systems.
Software Imagination and Vision - SIMAVI	Anomaly Detection is a component that raises alerts when anomalous or suspicious activities are detected in a network.
Software Imagination and Vision - SIMAVI	Data Traffic Monitoring is responsible with threat identification by monitoring the network traffic and applying signature-based detection analysis. It monitors all the packets traversing the network and compares them against a database of attack signatures or attributes of known malicious threats.
Software Imagination and Vision - SIMAVI	Interactive Dashboards is a component that centralizes and converts data i.e. web traffic, alerts in different types of graphical representations (tables, graphs, diagrams and custom plugins) to offer users a faster and more compact interpretation of an IT system.
TECNALIA	The Blockchain-Based Threat Registry platform is a state-of-the-art shared registry, which uses blockchain technology to share information between parties in real time. It also manages permissions in order to control who can access this information.
Intracom Telecom	Integration middleware among different software components.
KT	The proactive functionality of the Sphinx DSS is the core one of the DSS's. The end-users could stop an upcoming attack by simply blocking the attacker's IP or Port. In this case, the system will continue to operate as usual without being affected by the attack.
TechInspire	We developed a partial ³ homomorphic encryption based searchable encryption tool that ensures user data privacy and security. It allows participating entities to share data among their peers using a double sided blinded search approach.
Hellenic Mediterranean University	We designed and developed an automated vulnerability assessment service, which discovers existing network-enabled entities, performs periodical vulnerability assessments on them and propagates its findings, in the form of STIX2.0, to a message broker
AIDEAS	The MLID component is an add-on to the Honey Pot (HP) component. It received data from the HP and determines if a cybersecurity attack is taking

³ A fully homomorphic solution allows you to perform arithmetic operations in the encrypted domain. This means that one can execute an addition or multiplication operation in the encrypted domain and it would result in the same outcome as if these operations were performed in plain text. Having these capabilities opens multiple venues for the use of a fully homomorphic encryption solution but it all comes at the cost of computational complexity. The time and the amount of resources it requires to ensure that these operations can be performed in the encrypted domain undermines the useability of a fully homomorphic encryption solution. In order to overcome this, we prefer the use of a partial homomorphic encryption solution. A partial Homomorphic Encryption (HE) solution can perform either a multiplication or an addition operation in the encrypted domain. This compromise in capabilities limits the uses of the solution but reduces time and resource overheads. In the partial HE solution implementation for the SPHINX toolkit, we use multiplicative homomorphism to ensure that a search operation can be performed in the encrypted domain. The use of partial HE ensures that SPHINX toolkit would not be resource expensive and it would be easy to deploy the solution in a wider set of environments.

Name of Organisation	Innovation description
	place. Further it classifies the attack into 4 categories. The results of the MLID is sent back to the HP who send the results to the DSS.
EDGENEERING	The SPHINX API for Third-parties enables providers of medical devices or specialised clinical software to programmatically access available SPHINX services (anywhere and anytime) and validate whether their devices, systems or applications meet SPHINX's cybersecurity standards.

- Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Technology transfer

Most of the innovation owners' have transferred the technology that is needed to bring the innovation to or closer to the market. A 30% of the owners' states that they find this desirable and 20% percent that they have not as their innovation is open source or it is intended for their internal needs only.

- Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Engagement by Industrial research team of one of their company's business units in project activities

While some of the partners have managed to engage their industrial research team(s) the majority, while desirable, have not proceed in this direction; this is mainly explained because most of the innovations have a low TRL target (e.g. TRL4) or aim to provide their innovation as open source.

10. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Pilot

Most of the partners have planned this in the project's context as feedback from pilots can provide significant insights and as such assist the innovation owners to carry out the needed improvement and remedy actions that will further increase their innovations' maturity and market readiness levels.

11. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Capital investment (VC, Angel, other)

More than half of the partners find this desirable whereas the rest state that it is not yet planned as most probably the innovations are in low TRL level (as also stated in the DoA) that may be not so attractive for these types of investors.

12. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Investment from public authority (national, regional)

More than half of the partners find this desirable whereas the rest state that it is not yet planned partially explained from the previously answers that indicate there is no aim to bring the innovation to the market at all.

13. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Business plan

Most of the partners find this desirable and some of them have planned to do this in the project's context.

14. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Prototyping

In the project's context most of the partners have performed or planned the step of building prototypes of their innovations; these prototypes are utilized during the testing and demonstration activities to gather valuable feedback enabling as such the continuous improvement of the innovations paving the path to the market.

15. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Market study

Most of the partners indicated that this step was planned to be undertaken in the project's context.

16. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Demonstration or Testing activities

Steps to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Demonstration or Testing activities

Most of the partners indicated that demonstration or testing activities were planned and/or were carried in the project's context providing in the process essential feedback for the innovations' continuous improvement that would pave the way to or closer to the market.

17. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Feasibility study

Steps to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Feasibility study

Most of the partners find this desirable and some of them have planned to do or already done this step in the project's context.

18. Indicate the step(s) already done (or are foreseen) in the project in order to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Launch a start-up or spin-off

Steps to bring the innovation to (or closer to) the market: Launch a start-up or spin-off

More than half of the partners find this desirable whereas the rest state that it is not yet planned partially explained from the previously answers that indicate there is no aim to bring the innovation to the market at all.

19. Indicate which participant(s) (up to a maximum of 3 key partner(s) in the project delivering this innovation. For each of them, identity under the next question their needs to fulfil their market potential.

Besides FINT and AIDEAS that have indicated each as other as potential partners in the SPHINX AI honeypot innovation, all other answers indicate as partner the innovation owner.

20. Indicate their needs to fulfil their market potential:

Indicate their needs to fulfil their market potential

The majority of the partners indicate as the most important need the partnership with other companies, nevertheless the introduction to investors and IPR advice are deemed also important.

21. When do you expect that such innovation could be commercialised?

From the partners that aim to commercialize their solution the majority anticipates that this will be possible in 1-2 years following the project's completion; another 33 expects that this will be possible after an even longer period (3-5 years). Finally, there is a portion of the innovations that is anticipated to be ready for commercialization in less than a year.

22. Which partners are in discussion with investors (or are planning such discussions)?

PDMFC has stated that is or is planning to start such discussions. In addition, FINT indicated that plans to try to secure further funding (EU or private based) to reach TRL7 first and then TRL9.

4 The Sphinx Scientific Roadmap for Cybersecurity in Healthcare

4.1 Scientific Management

One of the goals of the SPHINX project is to devise a scientific and innovation roadmap that provides incremental steps necessary to achieve the SPHINX vision and guidelines to assist healthcare providers, industry and scientists to address externalities in order to improve innovation and competitiveness. The scientific roadmap, along with the community being built around it, focuses on giving good practice messages about technological issues in cybersecurity, and in particular to hospitals and the suppliers of medical devices, which have been selected by the SPHINX cybersecurity community as the ones to be addressed first. The scientific roadmap focuses on the steps necessary for realising the most optimum use of cyber security techniques, toolkits and methodologies.

4.1.1 Key Performance Indicators

The Scientific/Technical (S/T) dimension focuses on assessing the alignment of the R&D activities to what constitute current and long-term concerns from a scientific/technical point of view, and thus, in being relevant, timely and adaptable. The S/T dimension also assesses the excellence of the R&D work, as a combination of high quality and relevance.

4.1.1.1 Project R&D Excellence

The Project R&D excellence is an indicator that assesses the relevance of the project investigation and research developments by looking at their perception and impact within the R&D community. This assessment consists in measuring production, i.e. the quantity and frequency of dissemination activities of the Consortium members, but places a special emphasis on the quality of these publications, i.e. the specialized research capacity shown and the impact caused, for example as follow-up opportunities that may arise. The following are tools to measure R&D excellence:

- Bibliometrics: provides reliable data (on an aggregate level) of both production (quantity) and scientific impact (quality):
 - Average of Relative Citations (ARC);
 - Number of accepted publications in conferences and journals.
- Number of accepted publications in top tier ranked conferences, journals or venues (A*, A, B) (Conference Rankings , n.d.) (htt3) (htt4)
- Number of talks and presentations given to a specialized audience, co-located sessions;
- Presence of the project in events of relevance and high impact;
- Collaboration with other related projects and initiatives (nature and quality):
 - Peer reviewed publications;
 - Publications co-authored with at least one author external to the project;
 - Joint-workshops, joint-networking sessions;
 - Cross-references in official dissemination means (e.g., website, LinkedIn group, presentations).
- Contribution to designing educational programmes, creation or participation in summer schools or related teaching courses, creation of masters/ degrees, webinars, tutorials including fully/partially content developed in the project.

These indicators are consistent with the EU strategy for dissemination and communication of research activities in H2020 (European Commission, 2014) . Therefore, these indicators will mainly assess the activities carried out

in “Task 8.1 Dissemination activities” mainly, but also in “Task 8.3 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans” because of its objective to reach a wide audience and create high impact and awareness besides R&D community. Excellence implies consistently producing research that, according to one’s peers, makes an important contribution to the field of study in question. In addition to creating impact within the R&D community, R&D excellence can also make an impact in policy development, which benefits from high quality research achievements. Public administration’s demand for research results is increasing since that may help to legitimise policy measures and influence interest groups outside of the state and other centres of power in civil society. R&D excellence has also a societal dimension component: ensuring a high-quality contribution that the dissemination of SPHINX research makes to social development promoting a research culture.

4.1.1.2 S/T Continuous Alignment

The SPHINX proposal incorporated a very preliminary analysis (non-exhaustive) of the state of the art of cyber security technologies and solutions. However, a comprehensive scientific technology watch over all aspects related to cyber security that may arise along the three years duration of the project, is out of the scope of this Scientific and Innovation Roadmap, because of the lack of resources necessary and second, because putting a watchdog in every advance of a broad field such as cyber security would not guarantee a success from an innovative point of view. To this end, it is necessary to identify the strategic objectives for the S/T Watch that (i) are oriented towards meeting existing research gaps in the field of cybersecurity in the healthcare sector and, (ii) target priority and mandated issues that reflect both the current and the long-term scientific-technical concerns of the EU. To measure S/T alignment of SPHINX key innovation points, the Scientific and Innovation Roadmap will closely monitor the following instruments that regularly provide an insight on current research and technological gaps and reflect long-term, on-going objectives at the EU-level:

- EU Digital Agenda (European Commission, 2013)
- NIS WG3 Strategic Research Agenda (ENISA, n.d.), secure ICT landscape;
- Trust in Digital Life (Trust in Digital Life, n.d.) ecosystem.

Assessing S/T alignment means also measuring the adaptability of the SPHINX technologies, and the models and algorithms in which these technologies are built upon. Evaluating their capacity to respond to new emerging concerns, both scientific and political, and to adjust the R&D directions as new technological paradigms and models arise, contributes to increase the probabilities of technology adoption and a successful innovation. Some of the aspects to assess are the use of standards, and model-driven methodologies for the design of the primitives. The use of Agile software development techniques also promotes adaptive planning, evolutionary development, early delivery, continuous improvement, and encourages rapid and flexible response to change (Agile Alliance, 2013).

4.1.2 Process

This Roadmap is focused on the cyber security’s role across five main assets of Healthcare sector (aligned with ENISA report) (ENISA, 2016) which are the (i) healthcare staff, (ii) medical devices (personal or not), (iii) Hospital Equipment, (iv) Hospital Information System (Patient Records), and (v) Hospital legacy IT infrastructure (e.g.servers, PC, laptops). It will achieve this by:

- presenting growth-enabling themes and actions based on industry consultations that position cyber security as a growth-enabling business activity;
- developing a framework that can be applied to the aforementioned categories, and then be translated for rapid assessment across any sector within Healthcare’s economy;
- providing examples of how the framework can be applied to high-growth opportunities across the five identified Healthcare core assets.

Finally, this Roadmap will help the European Healthcare Domain to:

- identify how stakeholders can better understand and leverage cyber security for growth;
- allow cyber security organisations to understand sector needs and develop competitive and exportable offerings.

4.1.3 Guidelines and frameworks for Trusted Healthcare Ecosystems

SPHINX will work with Healthcare stakeholders to develop guidelines for best cybersecurity hygiene practice that is harmonized with key international guidance and standards to ensure superior security service, commercial interoperability and global market application (e.g. ISO in the EU). These guidelines should take into account the set of security practices recommended for the healthcare sector as set by ENISA, and the EU's data privacy guidelines to help businesses define and classify data, identify vulnerabilities in processes, and recommend minimum practices that will help to protect data and manage the supply chain implications of cyber threats. Guidelines should also help companies understand the importance of both sharing threat intelligence and monitoring information-sharing networks. These guidelines will need to be adapted to each industry while providing for a baseline of common practice.

4.2 Threat intelligence sharing for devices and systems

A trusted ecosystem can be developed by sharing threat information and working collaboratively with healthcare peers and government to understand the most appropriate methods to mitigate threats. In healthcare services and the supply of medical devices, information regarding cybersecurity is shared between competing organisations through local communities such as the national contact points (NCPs). This occurs as each organisation understands that the net benefit of collaborating to mitigate existing and emerging cyber threats is significantly greater than attempting to do so alone. The rationale behind this is straightforward: while a successfully deployed attack on a single major healthcare institute would destroy its brand and reputation overnight, there is a very high chance that the same attack method may be successful for multiple institutions, which means they are all vulnerable to losing significant value. Research suggests that 61% of customers would stop using a business's products or services if a cyber-attack resulted in a known security breach (PWC, 2015) ([htt5](#)). Even in the event that the competing institutions are not vulnerable to the same attack, the public perception of the entire sector will have been tarnished. This means that the entire healthcare sector has significant value-based motivation to ensure that they openly share and understand cyber threats. Translating this behaviour to other sectors in the same vertical is not straightforward. There are many challenges that need to be overcome: competitive industries often do not share information where commercial gain is not clear; there may be legal and privacy restrictions on what can be shared; and there is a potential for reputational risk. Building a culture involving sharing threat information whereby one organisation's detection of a threat can lead others to successful mitigation will require significant industry maturity. Industries such as healthcare organisations and individual medical device suppliers lack the digital maturity required to effectively assess their threat landscape, and generally do not share cyber threat information. SPHINX ecosystem will provide motivation to increase threat information sharing within the healthcare sector; however, it is based on driving compliance rather than protecting and increasing value within sector. Overcoming this provides an opportunity for purposeful inter- and intra-sector collaboration and in the SPHINX project we intend to deploy blockchain technology to reach precisely that goal.

Information about cyber threats will be shared within healthcare industry efficiently, thereby allowing credible threats to be identified and risks to be quickly understood. Appropriate systems will be in place to protect the confidentiality of reporting organisations (where necessary) and the integrity of the information, with incentives to encourage the appropriate level of threat intelligence sharing within and across healthcare sectors

creating a ‘competitors as collaborators’ mind-set. SPHINX will contribute in the following actions as part of its Scientific and Innovation Roadmap.

4.2.1 Data Sharing Frameworks (short-term/ 1-3 years)

The blockchain design pattern is increasingly adopted in many different scenarios as it could solve a complex replication problem: how different entities could trust each other by having the same copy of relevant data. In the context of SPHINX, relevant parties are **healthcare organizations, individual medical device suppliers and possibly future cybersecurity certification authorities / Conformity Assessment Bodies** which could all be legally obliged to keep a log of all privacy-critical operations performed by SPHINX users. This data must be protected against tampering and must be available to each participating SPHINX user; also, there should be a mechanism to reach consensus between all the users regarding the operations that have been performed by the users on the system.

Following these constraints, it is clear that a single centralized log management and auditing system is not feasible, both for technical reasons (as it introduces a single point of failure) and for organizational and possibly legal reasons (each entity must have a copy of the data under its direct control and each entity should not be forced to trust others’ management procedures). A blockchain-based approach could successfully be tailored to this context, following the general idea outlined below. Each user has one (or more) log system that concentrates and stores all the relevant descriptive information of the operations performed by SPHINX users that are relevant for the healthcare ecosystem or generally critical for the SPHINX system. Each operation that is performed by system users that results in an exchange of patients’ data (or as described below just SPHINX’s assets’ data) or has security or privacy implications is logged by all of these nation-wide log systems. Each one of these systems periodically collects all the received logs into a block, adds a timestamp and performs a digital signature of the block. As such, this single block could be later produced as a legal binding evidence of the operations performed by a single user of the system. The block itself is protected against deletion or forging by concatenating it to the next block. As more log entries are added to the log system, new blocks are added to the block chain and each block starts with the hash of the previous block. If one of the blocks is forged or deleted, all the following blocks will no longer be valid and an alert will be raised. Although this approach results in each user having a trusted, not forgeable, legally binding stream of log entries describing the privacy relevant operations performed by SPHINX users, it is still possible to compromise the log entries. An attacker has only to delete the entries from a (stored) block up to the current block, amputating the block chain and removing evidence of previously stored operations. This risk could be mitigated at an operational level, with methodologies and technologies easily available in the market (like server hardening and backup techniques). SPHINX will extend in an innovative way operating at an architectural level and leveraging the multiplicity of the log systems that are operated by the healthcare organization administrative staff.

The approach described above is only one of many that can be used and exploited using blockchain technology (or more generic, distributed ledger technologies, of which blockchain is just one example) and in fact SPHINXs intends to initially use blockchain technology to design a robust auditing mechanism for creating an advanced threats registry shared by all stakeholders. In this approach no patient’s data is ever transfer (that is not the purpose of the registry).

4.2.2 Collaborative Testing and Safe Execution Environments – Sandbox (medium term/ 3-5 years)

SPHINX aims to increase engagement with international companies and governments with a goal of sharing information about cybersecurity threats and vulnerabilities. Also SPHINX will try to leverage the expertise of the research community in this effort to ensure an ‘over the horizon’ perspective is built in.

SPHINX toolkit will propose a methodology which enables the power of formal methods to be exploited without any specialist training. By using tools such as SPHINX Sandbox (and external tools that allow formal modelling of Privacy and Security by Design software artifacts), it will be possible for engineers to develop software systems architectures in a rigorous manner, whilst gaining as a by-product the required evidence to confidently support system release.

After the medical component/device registration process in the SPHINX Sandbox, the Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS) module will approve that requirements will have been correctly captured as the reference design of the candidate medical component expressed in the SPHINX Sandbox, or will demonstrate the manner in which compliance has failed. The design can be of a System of Systems, a single system or a software program. It allows a designer to check that the design does what is required. More importantly, it allows a proof that undesired properties will never happen, a check that is typically attempted at the end of a development life-cycle. It is also possible to show behaviour under failure conditions. VaaS Module will take into consideration the behaviour of highly distributed Systems-of-Systems, including the behaviour of human interaction where necessary, by following specific predefined scenarios.

4.3 Device and platform security

IoT devices are often insecure by design, which creates significant vulnerabilities in the community. It is essential that cybersecurity implications are considered early in the design phase of all new technologies, processes and systems. Rigorous and early assessment of cybersecurity vulnerabilities allows for adaptable security measures and helps to define how much effort should be expended on overcoming a particular vulnerability. This is critical as security has a cost associated with it, and hence the value gained from incorporating security needs to be balanced and understood early in the development process. Incorporating secure-by-design principles and implementing good cybersecurity practices will, over time, allow healthcare organisations to create a competitive advantage for products and platforms that are developed onshore. As privacy and security issues move from being a post-development consideration to a design-phase consideration (Privacy and Security by Design), a shift particularly relevant in the healthcare sector, public trust, especially when it comes to personal data privacy will increase, complete product lifecycle cost will be reduced due to significant reduction in security and privacy data breaches, and the reputation of the products and services being developed using key components of the SPHINX toolkit will increase. Security by design will also underpinned in the long-term objectives of building a trusted ecosystem and a robust and resilient industry, thereby allowing Healthcare organisations and medical device suppliers to build a business model and competitive advantage around strong cyber security practices. SPHINX will contribute in the following actions as part of its Scientific Roadmap.

4.3.1 Embedded components for advanced threat detection (immediate)

SPHINX will develop frameworks with recommendations for baseline cyber security that should be built into any platforms or devices that capture and transmit data (SIEM, Sandbox, VaaS). This could be part of an international effort to better manage ICT supply chains using Healthcare pilots as a test case.

4.3.2 Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (short-term/ 1-3 years)

SPHINX will introduce an Edge-Based, Cybersecurity vulnerability assessment and mitigation framework, that will monitor devices and services in real-time and assess possible known or unknown cybersecurity threats. In case of any threat or vulnerability discovery, SPHINX will dynamically initiate and inform the SPHINX defence mechanisms to deploy the appropriate countermeasures or to address that threat or vulnerability, in terms of active mitigation or pro-active avoidance.

4.3.3 Advanced Honeypots (short-term/ 1-3 years)

In SPHINX, an advanced “honeypot” type of virtual component will be implemented. The proposed AI Honeypot will provide data dynamically to the detection algorithms, to detect anomalies and malware installed on the healthcare provider’s IT infrastructure. The main objective of this module is to discern the presence of malware associated with a device or subsystem which is connected to the healthcare IT environment under protection. To generate the algorithms, the SPHINX system must generate a dataset of malware, studying the malware signature-based and the behaviour-based that is deemed necessary, and analysing the results. In the learning process, the samples will be studied in depth by analysing both static and dynamic characteristics. Since the Artificial Intelligence (AI) Honeypot shall be used to automatically detect attacks, it will have the capability to recognize execution behaviour that is linked to attacks, such as execution-on-stack and execution-on-heap. The proposed solution would include a hypervisor solution that enables integration of the AI Honeypot. The SPHINX AI Honeypot would have value in situational awareness applications where network security status is tracked and analysed by specialized devices.

So, SPHINX Threat Intelligence Honeypots will:

- a) Detect only the "bad" traffic;
- b) work as farms making easier the deployment of such kind of solution in an organisation (enhanced scalability);
- c) Dynamic reconfiguration either by self-configuration learning from network, and/or supporting reconfiguration directly from the SPHINX's situation awareness system.

4.3.4 AI on Threat detection (medium term/ 3-5 years)

SPHINX will make a step forward developing an intelligent defensive system capable to either detect existing threats or even learn new uncategorised ones (Unknown threads copy attack patterns from Known threads but will be able to combine two or more known attack patterns) mitigating the possibility of an intruder teaching the system to consider its attacks as normal data. The proposed system combines honeypots to gather attack information from intruders and supervised deep learning algorithms for dynamic learning of both registered and unregistered data. Honeypots will be used to collect interaction data generated by attackers, whereas supervised deep learning will eliminate the need of manual and continuous updates of databases, as typically performed in traditional intrusion detection systems.

A four-steps methodology is employed to accomplish the implementation of the hybrid system: (1) Data collection: by getting logs/attacker data and signatures from the honeypots for further analysis, (2) Feature selection: to extract and identify important information from the collected honeypot logs, (3) Learning: The selected information is used to train the deep learning algorithms so as to be able to alert network administrators about incoming attacks. (4) Classification: The trained system can be seen as an early detection functioning intrusion detection system that can flag in almost real-time classifying traffic generated from honeypot interactions.

4.3.5 Automated CyberSecurity Certification (medium term / 3-5 years)

Addressing the expected skills gap in cyber security is critical to the successful growth of robust and resilient Healthcare organisations and industry. To help address this shortage, some partners from SPHINX intend to deliver automated device and service-based cyber security Certifications. The automated device cybersecurity certification, will follow the steps of the work being developed by ENISA and the official publication of the EU Cybersecurity Act. The EU Cybersecurity Act establishes an EU certification framework for ICT digital products, services and processes. The European cybersecurity certification framework enables the creation of tailored and risk-based EU certification schemes. This certification (to be issued by a Conformity Assessment Body which

some SPHINX partners will apply to become) will be complemented by Training in ethical hacking (considered a mandatory aspect to achieve the highest assurance level of certification) (Schaffer, 2018), (European Union).

4.4 Future research priorities

SPHINX aims to see Healthcare Industry become a world leader in digital transformation by leveraging data to deliver new solutions. This supports the opportunity for novel diagnostic and informatics products and services, and will require a strong focus on cyber security to allow consumers and healthcare providers to have trust in digital health applications. The SPHINX aims also to protect national digital health systems and personal health information of citizens from cyber threats, and to raise the security posture of the Healthcare sector. Any actions suggested in this document consider and build on the activities currently underway in the SPHINX and the other approved SU-TDS-02-2018 projects, especially frameworks for secondary data use under health medical records. This will accelerate the development of new platforms and solutions by facilitating secure, trusted data sharing between hospitals, health providers, medical technology developers and consumers. To be noticed that most of the future research priorities listed below are not going to be implemented in the scope of the SPHINX project, but are being considered by at least one SPHINX partner and might be developed by such partners but outside the scope of the project.

Research priorities underpinning these actions include:

- **Innovation in digital identity management and endpoint authentication:**

Re-using STORK 2.0 identities to leverage the existing user base, practices, software and systems. SPHINX **will not** develop its own eID schema but some of the partners of SPHINX it will leverage their developments on existing practices.

Properly managing of the STORK 2.0 identities: one specific partner of SPHINX (PDMFC) will take a comprehensive approach to the managing of eIDs, where each functional components of the system will deal with eID according to applicable procedures;

Adoption and integration of the electronic Identification, Authentication and trust Services (eIDAS) eID framework into SPHINX; SPHINX will be future-ready to maximize return from the project.

- **User-friendly and secure data access and data privacy solutions**

In SPHINX, each log entry is stored in at least two different log systems: one managed by the country where the operation is actually performed (country of operation) and one managed by the country where the data is actually stored and retrieved (country of origin). Critical operations for the entire SPHINX system could be recorded by many (or all) of the NCP log systems. This allows for a simple yet effective duplicating of the information, allowing each NCP to keep a complete and coherent view of what's happening. Second, each log system broadcasts the hash of the previous stored block to all of the other log systems and at the same time stores the hashes received by other log systems as specific log entries. As such, if one or more blocks are deleted, the confrontation between the hashes of the (newly formed) blocks and the hashes as recorded by the other log systems will result in a mismatch. As new blocks are periodically produced by the log systems, the window of opportunity for an attacker to tamper the data is drastically reduced resulting in a secure store and dissemination of relevant information.

- **Securing data in motion, including data communication routes, encryption of data and secure and privacy-preserving data linkage.**

SPHINX will build a dual-purpose homomorphic encryption mechanism (HEM) which, combined with more lightweight symmetric encryption schemes, will reinforce security levels at both runtime (data transmission/exchange and processing) and rest mode (data storage) during the lifecycle of citizens' health-related data.

Homomorphic encryption will be deployed in a coordinated manner to secure the computation on medical assets cybersecurity status record, keep stored in a secure manner using the symmetric encryption cryptography. It will enable secure execution of direct computational operations for (nearly) real-time health assessment and the application of medical predictive models, while maintaining confidentiality with data being remaining encrypted before, during and after processing. To this end, SPHINX's HME will encompass research work aiming at lowering the required computational power so that it can be used to outsource processing of sensitive data to an entity that is trusted to perform the computation correctly but without accessing the data.

- **Privacy by design in health informatics.**

SPHINX will apply rigorous data protection legal standards and procedures in order to mitigate the risks of infringing fundamental rights: privacy by design and by default implementations will be opted for against other technical alternatives, anonymized data will be processed wherever possible, and the principles of proportionality of the processing and data minimisation will be closely adhered to. In particular, with regard to cyber security issues and threats, SPHINX will contribute to fundamental rights protection by closely adhering to applicable law, and following guidance documents, best practices and standards (issued by international, European and national stakeholders) at all stages of design and development. Such documentation will be used in: (a) prioritising types of threats according to the likelihood of exposure and severity of consequences; (b) studying how already identified best practices can be applied and further strengthened through appropriate end-user behaviour; (c) elaborating the SPHINX reference architecture; (d) performing a gap analysis for cyber security solutions for the hospital IT infrastructure.

- **Data visualisation and advanced analytics, including privacy-preserving analytics.**

The following capabilities of the Enhanced Analytics Framework (EAF), a tool being developed by the partner PDMFC in the scope of an internal project called Large Scale Visual Analytics for Privacy (LESSY) can be deployed in a future SPHINX architecture:

- **Efficient processing of high-volume, high-velocity data:** EAF will incorporate efficient algorithms for online similarity matching in streaming data (real-time pattern identification). This basic operation will allow the processing of streams at very high rates, and will enable complex analytics on top of it, such as the real-time mining of approximate patterns in streaming data series, very useful in intrusion detection. In order to achieve high performance, future technology enablers will have the ability to integrate these algorithms with the capabilities offered by existing SPHINX Cloud Services. Big Data Series Indexing and Query Answering. When dealing with massive data series collections, indexing itself can become a bottleneck in a data series analysis task. The data series indexes we will develop will be able to handle much bigger data collections at shorter times, based on novel indexing techniques and the exploitation of the opportunities offered by new hardware (i.e., accelerators). This novelty in data science will outperform existing query times over vast amounts of data.

- **Visual and interactive analytics of IoT Data:** A useful feature of the SPHINX architecture will be the possibility of different partners to be able to implement complementary interactive analytics frameworks that allows users to work with a multitude of pattern classes and discovery algorithms. Integrated with SPHINX, such Visual Analytics component can offer to end-users an intuitive visual analytics tool and UI, which conceals from the user all data mining method selection and configuration steps while at the same time presenting IoT data in a meaningful and actionable format suitable for device activity monitoring.

- **Privacy-aware processing and data anonymization:** Data privacy and anonymisation will be a core part of the SPHINX architecture since it will maintain the privacy and anonymity of the users while allowing the lawful data reuse by various stakeholders in the SPHINX value chain. SPHINX via the EAF will provide the mechanisms for safely sharing, querying and analysing data between various

stakeholders by utilising suitable anonymisation algorithms that protect the privacy of the user while maintaining the value of the data. Coupled with suitable access control SPHINX can provide the means for secure and protected data sharing, curation and reuse. The employed anonymization methods such as k-anonymity or l-diversity are proven to guarantee privacy without compensating on scalability aspects since they can be parallelised. Furthermore, user privacy will be protected by building models of behaviour related to interactions that mine sensitive data. The interfaces are incorporated into EAF in support of an overall model and interface for privacy-aware mining.

- Advanced security for medical devices, such as personal wearables, implantable devices and medical equipment.

SPHINX introduces the concept of Vulnerability Assessment as a Service for newly entering IoT or Smart Objects in a health and care domain. In this way, SPHINX is building a Secure, Trusted and Certified environment that will be able to protect the Things that are assessed as “safe”. The SPHINX outcome will be a “re-engineered” systemic concept for greater security, addressing *international known or unknown threats* that entangle complex technoeconomic, political, social and psychological factors. SPHINX will achieve a minimised attack surface for the health and Care systems (IoT or not) by utilizing Artificial Intelligence, to employ the necessary countermeasures, in order to fortify crucial environments such as healthcare and homecare organizations/ infrastructures achieving a certified cybersecurity environment.

On the other hand, SPHINX Sandbox will be a security mechanism for separating running programs, usually in an effort to mitigate medical device failures or software vulnerabilities from spreading. The proposed shared environment often will be used to execute untested or untrusted programs or code, from unverified or untrusted third parties, suppliers, users or websites, without risking harm to the host machine or operating system. The proposed sandbox will provide a tightly controlled set of resources for guest programs to run in, hosted in SPHINX Cloud Backend.

- **Information interoperability solutions.**

In healthcare, interoperability is the ability of different information technology systems and software applications to communicate, exchange data, and use the information that has been exchanged. The SPHINX architecture will allow to distinguish between different levels of interoperability of health information. In the future we foresee the importance of using at least three levels:

- “Foundational” interoperability allows data exchange between systems without implying anything on the interpretation of the data.
- “Structural” interoperability is a type of interoperability which implies that providers exchange a common format for data exchange (i.e., the message format standards) and protocols for communication. This type of interoperability ensures proper interpretation of the data exchanged.
- “Semantic” interoperability is interoperability at the highest possible level, ensuring the ability of two providers to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged.
- Advanced threat detection solutions, including artificial intelligence.

SPHINX service portfolio will include a set of innovative cyber thread identification techniques, combining the benefits of the big data analytics (*big data analysis*) and the machine learning through the SPHINX Analytic Engine and Anomaly Detection Layer (*anomaly detection*) and modern ICT technologies to support *deep packet inspection* (deep packet inspection component) and *protocol services*. On the other hand, SPHINX **AI Honey pots** is expected to significantly increase the advanced threat identification capabilities of the proposed ecosystem.

5 Conclusions

The SPHINX Scientific and Innovation Roadmap described in this document suggests research and technical development as well as innovation activities in the short, medium and long term regarding the development of innovations of Cyber Security systems and components for the holistic design, planning and operation in the health care sector.

We proposed to use a well know mechanism (Innovation Radar) to periodically assess the innovation potential and the innovator capacity, focusing on the main innovations identified within the scope of the SPHINX project, in order to gain full awareness of their current status and develop improvement actions aimed to achieve all the innovation objectives of the project.

SPHINX innovation management is organised into three key phases namely the Exploration, the Definition and the Building of business case. The **Exploration phase** aims to identify core problems that the SPHINX project is trying to solve, the **Definition phase** aims to uncover the best ways to prototype and develop the underpinning technologies of SPHINX whereas the **Building a Business Case** phase, the aims to ensure that an investment in the innovations of SPHINX will see strong returns driving as such actual business growth for every organisation involved. In this direction, SCAMPER, Painstorming (Exploration phase), Key Knowledge Gaps (Definition phase), and SWOT and Horizons model (Building a Business case) methods were utilized for developing and deploying several questionnaires online for eliciting answers from the involved partners. Additionally, one more questionnaire that was based on the Innovation Radar Tool (we used 16 specific questions) to elicit the innovation Potential and the Innovators Capacity. The collected answers enabled for the compilation of a preliminary version of the SPHINX Business model, using the Business Model Canvas methodology followed by a more detailed version outlined in “D8.7 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v2” on M24 and in “D8.10: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3” on M36.

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